

ReCreate
Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy

Vullings et al.

**Best practice guidelines and
recommendations for reuse-
optimised deconstruction**

Publisher / project	Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy
Project acronym	ReCreate
Deliverable	D2.2 Best practice guidelines and recommendations deconstruction to optimised reuse
Lead beneficiary	TU/e
Author(s)	Vullings, M.W.F. (TNO), Huuhka, S. (TAU), Wijte, S.N.M. (TU/e), Lambrechts, T. (TU/e), Houtman, J. (Lagemaat), Landman, M. (IMD), Salmio, E. (TAU), Räsänen, A. (TAU), Jonker-Hoffrén, P. (TAU), Weijo, I. (Ramboll), Lahdensivu, J. (TAU, Ramboll), Stenberg, E. (KTH), Wedelsbäck, C. (HBH), Appelqvist, T. (HBH), Gudmundsson, K. (KTH), Dervishaj, A. (KTH), Westerlind, H. (KTH), Hernandez Vargas, J. (KTH), Henschel, C. (BTU), Fischer, J. (BTU) and Gottschling, D. (Ecosoil).
Dissemination level	Public
Cite this document	Vullings M.W.F., Huuhka, S., Wijte S.N.M., Lambrechts, T., Houtman, J., Landman, M., Salmio, E., Räsänen, A., Jonker-Hoffrén, P., Weijo, I., Lahdensivu, J., Stenberg, E., Wedelsbäck, C., Appelqvist, T., Gudmundsson, K., Dervishaj, A., Westerlind, H., Hernandez Vargas, J., Henschel, C., Fischer, J. & Gottschling, D. (2024). <i>Best practice guidelines and recommendations for reuse-optimised deconstruction</i> . The ReCreate project.
Disclaimer	The content presented herein reflect the authors' views. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information this publication contains.

Abstract

The ReCreate project researches deconstruction and reuse of precast concrete elements, not originally designed for disassembly. Real-life deconstructions of precast concrete buildings in four countries (Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands and Germany), performed by ReCreate's industrial partners as well as collaborators to harvest elements for reuse, were a key tool to gain experience and insights into deconstruction techniques and processes. The current report delivers an overview of what deconstruction entails. It gives best practice guidelines on the planning and implementation of deconstruction, as well as recommendations for improving the process.

While ReCreate's country-specific deconstruction pilots themselves are described in a dedicated report (Vullings et al. 2024), they are also briefly summarised in the beginning of this report. The focus of the current report is, nevertheless, on turning the learnings from deconstruction pilots into generalisable guidelines that can be capitalised beyond the ReCreate project and the parties involved.

Deconstruction entails four main phases: pre-planning, structural deconstruction planning, deconstruction work planning, and finally, implementing the deconstruction. This report instructs on the different types of plans involved in each stage as well as their authors and contents.

Pre-planning involves pre-deconstruction auditing, i.e. inventorying reusable elements and gathering relevant information into an 'inventory' Building Information Model (BIM). The pre-deconstruction audit has been covered by another ReCreate deliverable (Vullings et al. 2022), which was delivered before ReCreate's deconstruction pilots were fully complete. Therefore, the current deliverable briefly recaps the essentials of a BIM-based pre-deconstruction audit, and supplements and consolidates the findings of the previous report.

Authored by a qualified structural engineer, a structural deconstruction plan sets the foundations for a safe and efficient deconstruction process. It defines the deconstruction sequence based on structural stability; determines the need for temporary support and bracing measures; establishes cutting spots for connectors; gives a labelling scheme for logistics; instructs on correct lifting and transport of elements as well as how to monitor the quality of elements on-site; and can help to define requirements for stripping.

A deconstruction work plan, devised by experts of the deconstruction company, translates the structural deconstruction plan into work processes: both the overall deconstruction process as well as element type specific processes. It covers aspects like workforce, equipment, work safety, site planning and scheduling.

Finally, learnings acquired by implementing ReCreate's deconstruction pilots are elaborated on. Findings are reported on deconstructing different types of elements;

avoidable mistakes that were made which may influence the reusability (or at least the effort and cost of reuse) of the salvaged elements; the types of damage that is not easily preventable but an inherent part of deconstruction; and the influence of weather conditions on the deconstruction work. Additionally, special types of deconstruction projects are briefly discussed, such as partial deconstruction in the context of building remodelling, as well as combining deconstruction with conventional demolition.

While smaller, sub-process specific insights are scattered through the report, the main learnings of the key topics are distilled into checklists, given at the end of this report. The experience of the ReCreate deconstruction pilots shows that prerequisites for more widespread deconstruction already exist in that appropriately skilled workforce and suitable tools and equipment are widely available. The main technical and processual challenge in deconstruction is reconfiguring the existing know-how into safe and efficient deconstruction processes. This development can be further supported by small adjustments to existing tools that can help make the equipment even better suitable for deconstruction purposes. Nevertheless, it should be noted that a full evaluation of the success of ReCreate's deconstruction pilots can only be made once the salvaged elements have been reused in new buildings.

Acknowledgements

The following ReCreate team members provided background information on the ReCreate deconstruction pilots used in the writing of this report: Ronald Klein-Holte (VBI), Joost Puttenstein (Lagemaat) and all the deconstruction workers of Lagemaat. Jukka Kivimäki (Skanska), Hannu Tuukkanen (Skanska) and other Skanska site employees, also Antti Lantta (Umacon), Timo Kareisto (Umacon) and all Umacon deconstruction workers. Thanks also to Angelika Mettke (BTU), Viktoria Arnold (BTU), Axel Bretfeld (Ecosoil), Heikki Vuorinen (TAU) and Eetu Lehmusvaara (TAU).

Special thanks to Hans van Steen (Dycore) who, though not a member of the ReCreate project, was involved in the testing of the hollow core slabs and providing background information on the Dutch deconstruction pilot building 'Prinsenhof'.

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1. Introduction

The purpose of the ReCreate project is to study and facilitate deconstruction and reuse of precast concrete elements, not originally designed for disassembly. A key tool for this is the real-life deconstruction pilots of four donor buildings, which have been described in detail in a separate report (Vullings et al., 2024), though a brief overview is given in the next section. The purpose of the current report is to analyse and summarise the focal findings obtained through the deconstruction pilots. The current report is also underlain by an earlier report (Vullings et al, 2022) focusing on the possibilities of Building Information Modelling (BIM) during the preparation of deconstruction, which the current report supplements with further findings. The main purpose of the current report is to provide guidelines and recommendations on the following topics:

- Pre-planning using the donor building's BIM model (Chapter 2).
- Structural deconstruction planning, most importantly structural safety during deconstruction, disconnecting of connections, and lifting, (Chapter 3).
- Deconstruction and work planning, including staff and equipment to be used, work safety planning, and timetabling (Chapter 4).
- The deconstruction itself (Chapter 5).

The recommendations are presented in Chapter 6.

1.1. ReCreate's deconstruction pilots

The insights of the current report are based on the learnings from ReCreate's real-life deconstruction pilots, described briefly below and in more detail in Vullings et al. (2024).

1.1.1. Finland

The Finnish deconstruction pilot was an office building in the city centre of Tampere (Figure 1). The building was built in 1982 for an insurance company. In recent years, it was decided to change the land use of the site from offices to housing. This resulted in plans to demolish the office building. The ReCreate project partner, construction company Skanska, acquired the building and engaged it in ReCreate with the intent to deconstruct it and reuse the harvested precast concrete elements; mainly beams, columns, and hollow core floor slabs.

The building consisted of two parts, one with seven storeys and the other with only one storey. The precast concrete elements were harvested from the seven-storey section, which had a footprint of 29,6 by 14,7 meters and a total height of 25,5 meters.

The frame of the building consisted mainly of a load-bearing column and beam structure with some load-bearing exterior and interior walls (Figure 2). The facade elements were precast concrete sandwich panels, most of which had no load-bearing or bracing function. Hollow core slabs were used for floors and were positioned on the concrete beams. The

stability of the structure is derived from the load-bearing facade elements at the end of the building. In addition, at the other end wall structures of the stair chute brace the building. Floor slabs connect the load-bearing structures together and provide sufficient rigidity to the structure of the building.

Figure 1. Overview of the office building in Tampere (photo: Heikki Vuorinen, TAU).

Figure 2. Original structural design drawing of one storey of the building (source: City of Tampere archives).

1.1.2. Sweden

In Sweden, two buildings were used as donors to harvest precast concrete elements for reuse. The first building was a three-storey block of flats in Drottninghög, Helsingborg (Figure 3). The second building was an industrial building, a warehouse in Huggjärnet, Helsingborg.

Figure 3. An overview of the multi-family building at Drottninghög (left) (photo: Helsingborgshem). The industrial warehouse Huggjärnet (right) (photo: Municipality of Helsingborg).

A block of flats in Drottninghög

The block of flats was made up of several sections (one section is shown in Figure 4). A section had a width of 18,0 meters and a depth of 12,0 meters. The height of the building was 12,5 meters. The elements used in the building consisted of internal walls (indicated with the code 'V' in Figure 4) and floor slabs (indicated with the code 'P'). The stability of the building was ensured by the in-plane resistance of the internal walls and the diaphragm behaviour of the floor slabs.

Figure 4. A Section of the floor plan of one block (2 apartments) (source: Municipality of Helsingborg, amended).

An industrial building in Huggjärnet

The industrial building was a warehouse (Figure 5 right, purple area) combined with an office building (left, green area) with an entrance area in the middle, consisting of meeting rooms and a service area. A mezzanine (yellow) was located at the left side of the warehouse (indicated in Figure 5 with a dotted line). Only the warehouse part was deconstructed. It was 90,0 meters long, 29,0 meters wide and 6,5 meters high. Its structure consisted of precast concrete columns and beams. The stability of the structure was provided by internal walls.

Figure 5. Floor plan of the warehouse (right) and office building (left) (source: Municipality of Helsingborg, amended).

1.1.3. Netherlands

The Dutch donor building was the office building ‘Prinsenhof’ in Arnhem. It was built in 1987 and was owned and used by the Province of Gelderland (Figure 6). At some point the building became obsolete and vacant, so the province slated the building and issued a tender for its demolition. ReCreate partner Lagemaat responded with a bid to engage the building in ReCreate to deconstruct it and reuse the structural elements.

The nine-storey building was L-shaped (Figure 7) and consisted of three parts: two wings (A and B) and the core of the building (C). All the parts had different dimensions. The height of Wing A was 32,5 meters, the height of Wing B was 18,5 meters and the height of the core was 36,9 meters. The dimensions of the building are shown in Figure 7.

The building’s rather simple structural design, with a lot of repetition in the precast concrete elements, lent itself well to deconstruction. The wings of the building consisted of load-bearing facade elements with hollow core slabs, to which a structural topping was applied, spanning from one side of the wing to the other, a total of 13,0 meters. The core in the centre of the building consisted of internal walls and sandwich facade elements. The stability of

the building's structure was achieved by the cooperation between the floors and stability walls in the core and at the end of each wing.

Figure 6. Overview of the office building Prinsenhof at Arnhem (photos: Lagemaat [left] and Thijs Lambrechts, TU/e [right]).

Figure 7. Floor plan of the first storey of the building (source: Province of Gelderland, amended).

1.1.4. Germany

The German donor building was a block of flats (Figure 8) located in Hohenmölsen, near Leipzig. The building was built in the early 1980s using the 'P-Halle' precast system, an industrialised mass housing construction system from the former German Democratic Republic (GDR).

Some of these buildings have a lot of vacancies causing problems in the buildings themselves as well as their surroundings, such as trespassing and superfluous heating costs. Therefore the owner of the building, housing company WOBAU, decided to remove two storey's of the donor building to increase the occupancy rate of the remaining three storey's. There are many reasons for this, including a lack of demand from new tenants, high maintenance costs, ongoing operating costs and loan repayments, and a not insignificant reason to minimise unwanted building stock, i.e. subsidies for demolition. The ReCreate project became involved with the deconstruction of the top two storey's and the reuse of the harvested elements in other new buildings on other locations.

The building is approximately 100 meters long and 17 meters wide (Figure 9). It has five storeys and is divided into six sections. In each section, a stairwell provides access to three apartments per storey. The structure consists of precast concrete walls, facades and floors. Some internal walls are load-bearing while others are not. The stability of the building is derived from a combination of walls (in two directions) and floor slabs.

Figure 8. Overview of the German donor building (photo: Christoph Henschel, BTU).

Figure 9. Overview of the deconstructed structure (source: Christoph Henschel, BTU).

1.2. Types of plans in deconstruction

This report will refer to several types of documents and plans; a brief description of each type is therefore given to clarify the differences. The reader should note that these plans can be separate reports, or they can be combined into one report, depending on the needs of the deconstruction project. Different experts are responsible for compiling each plan, but the involved experts need to cross-check all plans to determine potential conflicts. Different views can also improve the quality of the plans.

Pre-deconstruction audit

Similar to a pre-demolition audit, a pre-deconstruction audit reviews the secondary resources salvageable from a slated building, but specifically from the point of view of deconstruction and reuse. It helps to identify and quantify salvageable structural and non-structural elements, structures and materials in the building, also taking into account factors restricting their deconstruction and reuse, such as the presence of hazardous substances or degradation. The pre-deconstruction audit can be prepared individually or collaboratively by different kind of professionals, but a joint effort of an architect, a structural engineer and a deconstruction expert is recommendable. A BIM-aided type of the pre-deconstruction audit is primarily discussed in a dedicated ReCreate report (Vullings et al., 2022). However, it is also touched upon in Chapter 2 of the current report.

Deconstruction plan

A ‘deconstruction plan’ is an umbrella term which refers to the combination of a structural deconstruction plan and a deconstruction work plan, including a health and safety plan and lifting, transport, and storage plans. In casual speech, the term may be used as a shorthand for either one of these plans. This is not recommendable, though, because it risks confusing which plan is actually meant.

Structural deconstruction plan

A structural deconstruction plan is a description of the various technical aspects involved in the deconstruction of a donor building that are relevant to the correct disassembly of precast concrete elements and the structural safety of the building during the entire process. A deconstruction plan may cover issues such as: deconstruction sequence of structural elements, and the use of temporary bracing and supports, and disconnecting different types of connections between elements. The plan is prepared by a structural engineer. It is discussed in Chapter 3.

Deconstruction work plan

The work plan covers all the steps and aspects required to carry out the actual deconstruction safely and effectively. It covers a wide range of topics, such as all staff and tools that will be used to deconstruct the building. It includes also a site plan with the location of the crane, the storage of the elements before they are transported, as well as designated area for loading of the lorries and the route the lorries will take. The work plan is discussed more in detail in Chapter 4.

Schedule and timetable

Schedule and timetable are also a part of the deconstruction work plan. Scheduling is a description of the sequence of tasks needed during the deconstruction. By adding the duration and time stamp of each task, a timetable can be generated, which helps to determine the expected duration of the deconstruction process from start to finish. The schedule and timetable are provided by the scheduling expert of the deconstruction company. The deconstruction work plan is discussed in Chapter 4.

Health and safety plan

A health and safety plan is a description of all safety measures and tools to ensure a safe working environment for the workers as well as outsiders throughout the deconstruction process. The health and safety plan describes all the necessary safety measures to prevent outsiders from accessing the deconstruction site and workers from harming themselves by e.g. falling of the building, falling into holes and shafts, as well as the use of safety clothing and equipment and what to do in case of an emergency. The safety expert of the deconstruction company writes the safety plan. Section 4.3 of the current report discusses the safety planning.

Lifting, transport and storage plans

This plan describes how to lift, transport and store all types of precast concrete elements properly, without damaging or breaking them. The plan includes the type of crane to be used for lifting, the location of the crane on site, the methods and tools to be used for lifting the different types of elements, accessories for lifting and transporting elements, and instruction for storing the elements. The plan should be devised in collaboration between a structural engineer, a safety expert and a lifting and transport expert. These aspects are discussed in Section 4.2.

Quality control plan

A quality control plan (upcoming ReCreate deliverables D4.1 and D4.3) gives an overview of the process of determining the quality class of harvested precast concrete elements and the structural properties of the elements, which determine the reusability and thus, functional and economic value, of the elements. The first part of the quality control is to determine, prior to deconstruction, if an element is worth to deconstruct or not. Here, the quality control focuses on the structural aspects, like determining the material properties, reinforcement, etc. of the elements to be harvested. Räsänen et al. (2024) describes the studies performed for ReCreate's donor buildings, while the future reports D4.1 and D4.3 outline a best practice proposal. The quality control plan can also include the evaluation of processes performed during the deconstruction – the focus of the current report – in order to limit errors, prevent damaging the harvested elements and make suggestions of improvement of the deconstruction processes. The quality control plan is drawn up by a quality expert (with a background in structural engineering) and/or the project structural engineer. Section 3.6 discusses the aspects of quality control to be performed on the deconstruction site.

2. Pre-planning with BIM model

The creation of an ‘inventory’ BIM model of the donor building can be an essential part of the pre-deconstruction audit, the benefits of which are discussed in Vullings et al. (2022). In this chapter, further development of the BIM model prior and during deconstruction works is discussed based on the experience gained through the Finnish and Dutch deconstruction pilots.

An inventory BIM model is a 3D model – a digital representation – of the donor building’s precast structure (Figure 10 and Figure 11), and it helps to create a detailed digital inventory of all the precast concrete elements in the building. The main purpose of creating a BIM model is to bring together all the available information about the donor building into a model that is easy to understand and contains detailed information. The information comes from archival research, design drawings and calculations, and inspections and measurements of the donor building itself. By creating a BIM model, the geometrical information is immediately checked for accuracy because any errors in the geometry result in clashes or gaps in the model. The information in the BIM model can be carried over to the subsequent steps of the reuse process, such as refurbishment of the elements and the architectural and structural design of a new building using the harvested elements.

While the standard EN 17412-1 outlines a framework for creating BIM models of buildings and structures in general, when inventory modelling donor buildings, gathering information on the structural elements takes a priority over other building components and materials. The ReCreate paper Dervishaj et al. (2023a) looks specifically at the use of BIM for the reuse of structures, and focuses on different aspects that relate to it, such as tracking and tracing of elements, classification, naming of elements, detailing, BIM-GIS data, etc.

Figure 10. BIM model (left) of the Finnish donor building (right) made as part of the pre-deconstruction audit. (sources: LIIKE Architecture [left], Heikki Vuorinen, TAU [right]).

Figure 11. BIM model (left) of the Dutch donor building (right) made as part of the pre-deconstruction audit. (sources: Cepezed [left], Lagemaat [right]).

2.1. Use of BIM models

The BIM model of the donor building can be used as a centralised storage space or as a database linking to documentation gathered during the pre-deconstruction audit. The model is typically generated based on archival documents from municipal archives or architects', engineers', suppliers' or contractors' records. The underlying data may include design documents such as drawings and calculations, as well as reports written at a later date as a result of the refurbishment, maintenance and previous inspections of the building. During the pre-deconstruction audit, investigations of the building are also carried out to verify and supplement the available information. This may involve the use of field measurements. Digital measurements, such as point clouds, can help speed up the process (Figure 12).

Figure 12. A laser scan (point cloud) of the Finnish (left) and Dutch (right) donor buildings made during the pre-deconstruction audit (photos: Heikki Vuorinen, TAU [left] and Lagemaat [right]).

Potential uses of the BIM model include:

- Checking the available geometric information for accuracy and completeness. Making a model reveals if the dimensions of a given element are not correct, so it helps to determine whether certain locations in the building require additional

investigation. If a geometric clash is observed, e.g. additional research of documentation or a site visit may be required to fulfil the data gap.

- Archiving all types of information, such as the geometry of the elements, including that of the reinforcement, material specifications, etc.
- Documenting structural health information, such as signs of visual degradation of materials or damage to the elements observed during site visits, in the BIM model. This helps to determine the suitability of an element for reuse.
- Storing the results of the various tests carried out on the elements at different stages of the process (e.g. during pre-deconstruction audit, deconstruction, or storage).
- Determining whether elements are suitable for reuse, not only based on the structural health of the elements but also on the geometric shape of the elements and their reinforcement properties (or the lack of knowledge thereof).
- Analysing the accessibility of an element, i.e. whether and when its connections can be physically accessed with deconstruction equipment.
- Analyzing and designing the method and order of the deconstruction of the elements in such a way that the structure remains stable and safe throughout the complete deconstruction process. The deconstruction sequence can be visualized using the BIM model.
- Determining the location for cutting the connections and elements so that they are not damaged in any way. Damage to an element can be a reason for disqualifying an element for reuse.
- Designing a temporary bracing plan for the structure during the deconstruction. This process may involve structural calculations.
- Determining the best location for a crane and other parts of the deconstruction site logistics.
- Making a summary of the environmental impact 'embodied' in the materials of the elements, based on the weight of each element and e.g. CO₂ coefficients of concrete and steel. This embodied impact models environmental savings achievable through reuse, as an equal amount of environmental impact is avoided by not producing new materials and structures.
- Analysing the need for refurbishment of the harvested elements, design of refurbishment measures.
- Transferring the 3D objects of the structural elements to BIM models of new building designs. This guarantees that all the original geometric and structural information is transferred. The inventory model is the most important and often the only link between the information on the salvaged elements and the new building where they are reused. The labelling of the physical elements is a critical part of the information link.
- Monitoring, tracking and tracing each element from a donor building, as they may be reused in more than one new building. This can also result in different storage facilities, refurbishment strategies, etc.

The list is not exhaustive, but it illustrates the potential benefits of a comprehensive inventory BIM model of a donor building. While the minimum requirements during the deconstruction phase consist of the elements' geometry and information on their connections, using the BIM model as a database to link various kinds of available data can vastly benefit the next phases of the reuse process, where this information is needed. The availability of information also determines the level of detail in the BIM model: less available information will result in a lower level of detail.

Different information will be relevant to different parties (e.g. the deconstruction company, architect, or structural engineer) during the steps of the reuse process (e.g. deconstruction, redesign, etc.). Different parties may also add available information to the BIM model during the reuse project. This may be done as part of work processes required for their own use, or to add value for others involved in the project.

Figure 13 shows filtered views of the Finnish deconstruction pilot's BIM model. Each element type has been modelled and is classified in a different way to visualise the different properties of the elements; in this case, the type and length of the elements. Such filtered views and colour schemes can be used for, for example, specifying if an element can be (or is) harvested for reuse or whether it is recycled.

Figure 13. Each element is modelled and classified in different ways to assist decision-making on deconstruction and reuse. The BIM model of the Finnish donor building. (source: LIIKE Architecture).

2.1.1. Level of detail

The basic information needed to create the most rudimentary version of an inventory BIM model consists of the geometry of the building and its precast elements. Many of the analyses and calculations described in the previous section can already be performed with just this information.

In addition to the geometric information, structural information is available in the drawings, calculations and reports. It is needed to design the correct locations for cutting joints and elements, and to design the structural stability of the building during deconstruction. However, this information does not necessarily have to be in the donor building's BIM model, as there are other ways to handle it. At the time of writing this report, it is not yet clear whether the extra effort and cost to include the additional data in BIM is directly beneficial to the deconstruction process itself. The two main arguments in favour of including it are:

1. The BIM model is a database for collecting all available information about the donor building and its elements. It is the only place where information is stored and can be accessed in a centralised manner, helping to avoid errors and ambiguities.
2. Only geometric information is not sufficient to determine whether the elements can be reused in a new structure. Material properties, reinforcement, damage, etc. must also be available. Including this type of information already in the BIM model can be beneficial. Having the information stored in one model (one database) reduces the potential for errors and information misplacement or loss. The availability and reliability of information is paramount for the value of each harvested element. Complete and reliable information guarantees successful and optimal reuse of a harvested element in a new structure.

The ReCreate paper Dervishaj et al. (2023a) discusses in more detail the Level of Information Need when reusing precast concrete. In practice, time and cost will limit the amount of information incorporated in donor buildings' inventory BIM models. As the number of deconstruction projects grows, the acquired additional experience may help to determine the cost-efficient level of detail in donor buildings' inventory models as well as the best way to store additional information. Automating the process of adding data to BIM models may also be helpful. In the future, artificial Intelligence (AI) tools may be able to assist in analysing documents (drawings, calculations, and reports) as well as inserting the information into inventory models.

2.2. Lessons learnt

Need for a BIM model

The need for some form of digital system to store, combine, access, and analyse information about the donor building and its elements is very clear. BIM provides the ability to share structured data in which building components have well-defined relationships with other data, allowing the information available to be effectively searched and filtered.

One advantage is that each digital building element in a BIM model has a unique identity, which can be linked through tagging to its physical counterpart and its characteristics. This can be further facilitated by the use of open and non-proprietary file formats and well-defined schemas for organising the data in the files.

The use of 3D BIM models is common practice in the construction industry. Nowadays the information in these models is used in all areas of construction, not only in architectural design but also engineering, manufacturing and on-site construction work. The benefits of digitalising information can also apply in deconstruction. In ReCreate's deconstruction pilots, several different digital systems were used, such as an Excel spreadsheet or a BIM model, but the ability to visualise the data in a BIM model and connect to the current practices gives a clear advantage. The standardised Industry Foundation Class (IFC) format can be used in a great number of tools and applications and do not require particular BIM software platforms.

Today, it is a common practice to use 3D BIM modelling in the design and engineering of new buildings and structures. This type of modelling will also be used when designing a new building with reused precast concrete elements, including ReCreate's reuse pilots. The possibility to transfer a donor building's precast concrete elements as digital objects from the inventory BIM model to the new building's model may help to reduce errors that could otherwise occur.

Confirmation of information

One of the first steps in the process of deconstruction and reuse of precast concrete elements is to gather information about the donor building and the (concrete) elements in the building. Drawings, calculations and reports are reliable sources of information, but there may be different versions which may contain conflicting and incorrect information, resulting in clashes or gaps in the BIM model. Correct information about the donor building and its elements is of paramount importance for the value of the salvaged elements. Therefore, it is necessary to confirm the information. One of the methods is to record all the collected information in a 3D BIM model. Errors in the geometry can be easily identified through clash checking.

Verification of information on site

3D modelling of the donor building can reveal formation defects, such as incorrect geometry, but is not always conclusive. Inspections and site visits provide additional information and confirmation. Site visits can provide clarification in cases where there is conflicting information in drawings and reports. Also, later changes made to a building and its structure do not always appear on drawings.

Confirmation of information after deconstruction

Deconstruction itself may change the elements, for instance due to the need to cut connections in order to detach them from the building. It may not be physically possible to cut exactly in the joint (e.g. because of the space taken by a saw), but the cut may need to be positioned in the element themselves (Figure 14). In addition to having structural

implications (which will be discussed in future ReCreate reports, deliverables D5.1 and D5.3), this shortens the elements. Another example is shown in Figure 15, where the focus is on the damage to the elements' reinforcement. It is recommended that the BIM model is updated to reflect these types of changes. They can be recorded in the elements' digital objects as extra information.

Figure 14. An example from a deconstruction pilot, where the columns were cut just above the column base joint. The column rebar (marked) is visible in the cutting plane. The starter bars and grout tubes are also visible (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO, amended).

Figure 15. The support of a beam in two walls is cut just below the beam-wall joint, via drilling cylinders. This damages the rebar and anchors in the walls. The effect of element changes will be discussed in deliverables D5.1 and D5.3 (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO, amended).

3. Structural deconstruction plan

A structural deconstruction plan is a detailed description of how the donor building should be deconstructed while maintaining the structural integrity of the building (and thus, a safe working environment for deconstruction workers in the building). It needs to be prepared individually for each donor building by a qualified structural engineer. Due to the unique nature of each building and deconstruction project, the plan must be tailored to the specifics of the building and the project in question. The aspects that a structural deconstruction plan should entail depend on the project, but would normally include:

- Special requirements for stripping ahead of deconstruction, e.g. due to the presence of harmful substances (Section 3.1).
- A labelling scheme of the precast concrete elements for later tracing (Section 3.2).
- Structural safety during deconstruction, including a safe deconstruction sequence and the need for temporary bracing or shoring (Section 3.3).
- Disconnecting the connections between concrete elements safely and without damaging the elements (Section 3.4).
- Instructions for safe lifting of the elements from the structural point of view. If needed, the structural design of special lifting accessories for deconstruction (Section 3.5).
- Instructions for safe transport and storage of the elements from the structural point of view (Section 3.6).

3.1. Requirements for stripping

Before starting the deconstruction process, the load bearing structure of the building must be stripped from all hazardous materials as well as non-structural materials. This is, in principle, a process that demolition contractors are familiar with, since it is also performed in demolition projects. However, the level of stripping required for deconstruction may also differ from that required for demolition, and rather resemble stripping done for a comprehensive remodelling and renovation of a building. This also depends on the context. Legal requirements, as well as how sorting and recycling of demolition waste is organised (and how that is reflected to the requirements for stripping), can vary.

Due to context specific features, a structural engineer's role in defining the requirements for the stripping may also vary. Since the engineer is intimately familiar with the load bearing and non load bearing parts of a building, he or she can help the contractor to identify the correct extent of stripping. Identifying the presence of hazardous substances in the donor building's construction materials is another topic that the structural engineer may be able to contribute, depending on the context. In certain context (such as Finland), some structural engineers specialise in performing hazardous substance surveys (including material sampling) in buildings, whereas in other locations, this may be a separate profession or a part of demolition contractors' expertise. How to deal with hazardous

materials in donor buildings is discussed as a part of deconstructed elements' quality management in Räsänen et al. (2024) and future ReCreate deliverables (D4.1, D4.3).

3.2. Labelling scheme

A labelling scheme is an essential part of the structural deconstruction plan. It is part of the structural engineer's work since a donor building may contain multiple versions of the same type of element (e.g. a column) that look outwardly similar but have differing technical properties. This is because the location of an element in a building has a relation with its structural capacity. For instance, the structural capacity of column at the bottom of the building will be greater than the capacity of a column at the top of the building.

In order to keep the technical information traceable in such cases, the elements must be labelled before they are deconstructed from the building. The labels link the items to their original locations in the donor building as well as to all data concerning them, such as material properties, reinforcement information, drawings, calculations, and test results. The labelling plan can also be embedded in the BIM model of the donor building. Whether the labels should be unique, i.e. individual to each element in question, or only distinguish between technically different elements, may depend on the situation. Retaining information about the exact location can be helpful for quality management purposes if different individual elements of the same type have been exposed to differing climatic conditions or harmful substances.

Figure 16 shows the syntax of the codes used to label each element in the Finnish deconstruction pilot. The syntax is described in the structural deconstruction plan. The code gives information about the type of element and the location of the element in the donor building. The code of a harvested element can be linked to information of each element in a database. Labelling drawings have also been made by adding the codes on top of the building's original drawings (Figure 17). Ideally, the labelling scheme builds on the original element codes of the donor building, if they are known.

Figure 16. Description of the code used in the labelling of each individual element within the donor building (source: Ramboll).

1. Cantilever action of columns: a column is fixed to the foundation by a moment-resisting connection.
2. Frame action: the use of rigid connections between columns and beams, resulting in a stiff structural frame.
3. Braced structures: cantilever cores, shafts and/or walls are used transfer all horizontal loads to the foundation of the cores, shafts and walls.
4. A combination of two aforementioned systems (1-3) to increase the number of vertical bracing elements and to so reduce the internal stresses in each vertical bracing element.

During the deconstruction process, the overall stability of the building must be maintained, which means that the original vertical bracing elements must be retained as long as possible. Therefore, the non-bracing elements should be removed first, followed by the bracing system. This is the basic deconstruction sequence.

External forces, such as gravity and wind, act on the building and cause the internal forces and stresses. A support is a connection between structural elements that transfers forces and stresses between elements. A restraint prevents lateral and/or rotational movement between the elements. There are three types of restraints: a) fixed restraints, which allow no movement, and forces can transfer; b) free restraints, where movement is allowed, so no forces are transferred; and c) spring restraints, where limited movement is possible and some forces are transferred. A support provides a restriction of movement (translation and rotation) in one or more directions.

Prefabricated elements are usually connected with dowel joints and form-fitting (interlocking) joints. Interlocking concrete forms are used to increase robustness of the structure and to transfer forces from one element to the other. In deconstruction, ties are typically cut to undo connections between elements and free an element, making it accessible for lifting. Figure 18 (top) shows an illustrative example of an elevation of one part of a precast concrete structure. This example showcases several interlocking elements, like the Walls 1 and 2 (Storey 3). After cutting all the connections in the horizontal joint, Wall 2 can be removed after Wall 1 is gone. Wall 1 prevents the removal of Wall 2 because of the interlocking corbel on the top right side of Wall 1.

The interlocking of the elements determines the logical order of deconstruction and the elevation shows more examples of interlocking elements. The numbers in each elements represents a logical deconstruction sequence, starting with Wall 1 and finishing with Wall 16.

Figure 18 (bottom) presents a deconstruction sequence and even though it is a logical sequence; it is not a structurally sound one when all three basic principles are considered. After removing Wall 4, the remaining structure is not structural sound. The restraint of the support of Beam 9 has been changed by removing Wall 4, the support is no longer fixed, it has become a pinned support Beam 9 can move upwards resulting in a partial collapse of the beam-column structure on the right side.

Figure 18. Elevation of the building showing all the precast concrete elements in the structure of a building. Problematic deconstruction sequencing. (source: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 19 presents a better deconstruction sequence that takes into account all the three basic principles. Each element can be removed taking interlocking elements into account. In the remaining structure, Wall 10 can be removed without causing the partial collapse of the structure (beams and columns). During the deconstruction, the vertical bracing walls (Walls 1, 2, 10, 11 and 14 – 16) keep providing the overall stability for the remaining building. These walls are the last elements to be removed from the structure.

3.3.2. Temporary bracing and supporting

Temporary bracing and supports (Figure 20) are required to ensure the stability of the donor building during the deconstruction process. Bracing and supports also required for new or changed loads, i.e. loads not considered in the design of the donor building, including loading during the construction phase. The structural deconstruction plan must specify the type of bracing supports, their number, as well as their locations and methods of attachment. This is determined by the structural engineer.

It is important to consider the impact of heavy machinery, such as demolition robots and waste containers, on the structural integrity of a building. These items, which may be used during the deconstruction process, can introduce new loads that must be accounted for in the design. The reassignment of a roof function to a lower floor represents another example of a change in loads (as evidenced by the German pilot project), and in cold climates, newly

Figure 19. A deconstruction sequence based on all three basic engineering principles; structural stability, changing restraints and free elements (source: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 20. Temporary braces for the facade elements are installed during the deconstruction process (source: Thijs Lambrechts, TU/e [left] and Lagemaat [right]).

introduced snow loads should be taken into account, if deconstruction is performed in the wintertime. The German pilot also considered the discrepancy in partial safety factors between the deconstruction phase and the service life of the structure. It is the responsibility of the structural engineer to consider both the new loads and any subsequent alterations

throughout the deconstruction phase. During this period, the remaining structure is susceptible to changes.

Temporary bracing and/or supporting can also be an alternative method for preventing partial collapse (as the one in Figure 18), as shown in Figure 21. Such measures can make the deconstruction sequence of Figure 18 feasible and safe.

Figure 21. Temporary supports (red) supporting Beam 7 and 6 prevent the partial collapse of the column-beam structure, even though the restraints of the left support of Beam 9 are changed by removing Wall 4 (cf. Figure 18). (Source: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

3.4. Disconnecting connections

A structural engineer has designed how a precast building’s elements have been connected, and this information has been recorded in the structural detail drawings of the building. Therefore, a structural engineer is also the best versed expert to consider if the connections can be untangled or where cuts should be made so that the element can be detached in a reusable condition. In doing so, the structural engineer should consult with the deconstruction company, because the skills of the workforce (Section 4.1) and equipment (Section 4.2) available for the work may influence which alternatives are feasible. If possible, it is advisable to pre-plan more than one alternative cutting spot and technique for disconnecting a given connection for contingency planning reasons. This way, the work on the deconstruction site can continue even if a given alternative is not feasible; otherwise the work might need to be stopped until the engineer has had time to reconsider the matter.

Connections between precast elements come in various types and depend on building type-specific technical demands in the donor building (e.g. load transfer, structural stability, fire safety, acoustic requirements, etc.) as well as production and assembly-related issues. The variety of connection types occurring in precast concrete elements is discussed in another ReCreate report (Hernandez Vargas & Stenberg, 2024). One of the most common ways to connect elements, though far from the only one, uses steel ties called starter bars, which are located in one element and protrude into a grout tube in another element (Figure 22). The tubes are filled with grout during construction and once the grout has set, a structurally sound joint has been achieved. The starter bar can be a

rebar cast in the bottom precast concrete element or can consist of two different parts. The first part is an anchor cast in the bottom concrete element and the second part is a rebar screwed in the anchor. The practical reason for the last method is that no protruding bars are present during production and transport of the precast concrete elements, making it safer. By cutting the starter bar at the joint, the connection can be disconnected. If the anchor system has been used, a new starter bar can be applied and a new connection can be made.

Figure 22. Typical connections between precast elements (front views). The alternative projecting rebar is a special anchor system cast in the bottom element and the top part is screwed in the anchor and cast into the grout tube in the top element (source: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Connections may also have been designed for disassembly (DfD), but this is presently rare. Therefore, the focus of ReCreate and the current report is on connections that have not been designed with this in mind. Non-DfD connections are overwhelmingly prevalent in the existing stock. Cohesive connectors, such as bars and bonds – as shown in Figure 22 – typically call for cutting and chiselling, which damages the connector. As a rule, deconstruction renders such connections non-reusable, requiring post-installed connectors to be developed for reuse, which is a topic of another ReCreate deliverable, D5.2. However, by using deconstruction methods that limit or eliminate the amount of damage to connectors, some non-DfD connections can nevertheless be categorized as reusable. For one, force-locking connectors, such as bolts, are examples of connections that may be disassembled without damage to the connector. Though not exhaustive, the next sections present a few examples of both types of connections encountered in the ReCreate pilots.

3.4.1. Non-reusable connections

Connections using cast-in ties (rebar), such as those in Figure 22, were typical non-reusable connections encountered in ReCreate. In deconstruction, the starter bars were cut at the joint (Figure 23). The connections are not reusable without additional measures, as the protruding parts of the starter bars are gone and the grout tube is filled with grout and the other end of the original starter bar.

welding a separate piece of connective rebar to two projecting bars. During deconstruction the connective rebar was cut, leaving the projecting bars undamaged. The projecting bars can be reused using the same connecting method, i.e. by welding a new connective bar. The ability to use welding as a reconnecting method is highly dependent on the steel grade of the cast in rebar. Some grades are not suitable for multiple heat induction, which can weaken the material properties of the rebar. In each situation, a structural engineer will need to determine whether welding is an option for reconnecting elements.

Figure 25. Top of three walls, each with a recess and projecting bars (left). The bars have been welded together. The mortar in the recesses can be chiselled out without damaging the rebar. A detail drawing shows the parts of the connection (right). Note: the implementation of the connection differs slightly from the designed one, but the principle is the same. (source: Jakob Fischer, BTU).

Figure 26. A clarification of the connection of three walls. Two starter bars protrude from the internal wall at the top of the photo (yellow/A). Four starter bars protrude from the external walls left and right (blue/E). Connective rebars have been welded to the starter bars (green/B, red/C and orange/D). (source: Jakob Fischer, BTU, amended).

The second example is the reuse of a specific part of a connection. As already mentioned, a starter bar in the in the connection shown in Figure 22 can be made of two parts, an anchor cast in the precast element (part A) and a rebar (part B) screwed into the anchor. Together, these two pieces make one starter bar. In one ReCreate's deconstruction pilots, a connection corresponding to Figure 22 middle was found to use such a two-piece started part. In the deconstruction, the starter bar part B was cut at the joint between the concrete elements leaving a small piece of part B in the anchor (part A). The small piece could be successfully screwed out of the anchor (part A), so the anchor (part A) could be reused (Figure 27) for lifting and is reusable for making a new connection in the future reuse pilot.

The third example is the connection between a beam and a wall/column, also using starter bars. The starter bar was cast into the wall/column, and it protruded into a grout tube in the beam. In this particular situation two ties were used to make the connection between wall/column and beam. The beam was positioned on top of the wall/column.

During the deconstruction, the grout tube was drilled out from the top of the beam with a hollow cylinder drill, detaching the starter bar (and the cylinder of grout attached to it) from the beam. The beam (Figure 28, left, blue arrow) was then lifted away, exposing the remaining starter bar in the column (Figure 28, left, red arrow). After lifting, much of the grout around the starter bar broke off, leaving only a small piece near the column. As a result of the drilling out, the grout tubes were restored (Figure 28, right, yellow arrows), enabling their reuse in the original fashion. Even the starter bar can be reused if the excess grout is chiselled away and the bar's structural condition is sufficient for reuse, i.e. if it is long enough, has the correct diameter and if the level of corrosion is acceptable. The structural engineer has to determine this, taking into account the forces acting on the reused tie connection in the new application.

Figure 27. The use of existing anchors cast in at the top of the wall elements. Special lifting loops were screwed into the anchors and used for lifting the elements (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 28. The end of the beam (blue arrow) has two grout tubes for two starter bars protruding from a column (left) or a wall, where they have been cast in. The two grout tubes at the end of the beam (right) are drilled out with a hollow cylinder drill (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

3.5. Lifting harvested elements

The main issue when handling heavy concrete elements is safety – the elements must not slip out of the lifting system, transport vehicle, or storage rack during the process (transport and storage of elements see paragraph 3.6). Industry guidelines typically exist for precast concrete elements, which may cover issues such as lifting, transport, and storage, and which may be used when formulating instructions for the site workers as a part of the deconstruction work plan (Chapter 4). However, due to the inherent risks involved, lifting also includes structural considerations that the structural engineer must undertake.

Lifting equipment

The lifting equipment, including any lifting accessories, must be designed to endure the loads they will be subject to in deconstruction. The same applies to the precast elements being lifted. Lifting accessories will often encircle or pierce an element, and a structural engineer must ensure that the element's material fabric will not crumble under the load the lifting subjects it to. Use of lifting equipment on construction sites is regulated, and lifting systems used in new construction are certified. Different types of systems for lifting precast concrete elements include (Figure 29):

1. Cast-in steel rebar loops (Figure 29A).
2. General specialised anchor systems (Figure 29B and C).
3. Product specific systems (Figure 29D).
4. Post-installed fasteners.

However, many of these may not be usable for lifting precast elements directly after deconstruction. In good condition, only the anchor systems (B and C) can be reused when lifting a deconstructed element from a building. The cast-in rebar loops (A) may be available for lifting, but using them is not recommended due to the high risk of damage, such as corrosion or multiple bending of the rebar (bending weakens the steel). Special product systems may not be usable directly after deconstruction because the system may

not fit onto the product, such a hollow core slab like in Figure 29D, when grout is still attached to the sides of the element.

Figure 29. Different types of lifting systems for concrete elements, (A) cast-in rebar, (B and C) special lifting anchors, (D) special accessories for specific elements like hollow core slabs (sources: ¹)

Therefore, alternative lifting systems are likely needed in deconstruction projects. This was the case in ReCreate’s pilots, too, where several different lifting systems were developed for hollow core slabs by the involved structural engineers (Figure 30). It is important to note that any newly engineered lifting methods and accessories must always be certified according to applicable regulation before they can be used. Similar approaches were used for lifting hollow core slabs, walls, columns and beams. Apart for the hollow core slabs, mainly standard lifting chains were used in combination with holes drilled in the elements for lifting, as shown in Figure 31. This way of lifting corresponds with the original lifting scheme of some elements, such as columns. Alternatively for some elements, original anchor systems could be reused (Figure 32). A structural engineer must always determine whether reusing the anchors for lifting is safe.

Figure 30. Newly developed lifting accessories for harvesting of hollow core slabs: the Dutch version (left) and the Finnish version (right) (sources: Lagemaat [left] and Ramboll [right]).

¹ (A) <https://www.ramjackokc.com/articles/how-does-smart-solution-work-for-concrete-lifting>
 (B) <https://www.eathu-precaster.com/lifting-loop.html>
 (C) <https://www.vbbeton.com/hijsvoorzieningen>
 (D) https://vbi.nl/downloads/?_document_type_download=brochures
 (document: 'VBI-Visiedocument Remontabel bouwen – deel 2')

Figure 31. Lifting by drilling holes in the elements (wall and floor) and treading a chain or a sling through the holes (or in the case of columns, a lifting pin – not shown in the images). (Sources: Christoph Henschel, BTU [left] and Ramboll [right]).

Figure 32. These walls are lifted with the original general specialised anchor systems. These special anchors were still accessible and usable after 35 years (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

If needed, a structural engineer can also specify post-installed fasteners (anchor system applied in hardened concrete, Figure 33) to be used as lifting anchors. It should be noted though that these fasteners come with a highly specific set of conditions and application guidelines, described in the Technical Specifications of each fastener as specified in the standard EN 1992-4. The structural engineer can also advise where the fasteners should be placed to avoid drilling into the reinforcement of the elements. Post-installed fasteners are also used as per the structural engineer’s instructions to attach bracing, shoring, scaffolding, etc., mentioned in section 3.3.

Figure 33. Special eyebolts can be used in combination with post installed fasteners like epoxy systems (photos: Kjartan Gudmundsson, KTH [left] and Hilti anchors² [right]).

Weights of elements

Weights of the precast concrete elements are necessary information for the safe lifting. Cranes have a lifting capacity that depends not only on the weight of the load but also the distance of the crane to the element being lifted (Section 4.4). In tower cranes, the lifting loads must be set in the crane’s computer before lifting. The weight information also helps the crane driver to determine whether an element has been disconnected properly. If the lifting force exceeds the weight of the element but the element is not moving, some connector is still attached. This can trigger a warning and the workers can make adjustments to disconnect the element properly.

The structural engineer can determine the weights, to be given as a part of the structural deconstruction plan, in a number of ways depending on the information available. Normally the weight of an element is given on the production drawing (shop drawing) of the element. If this information is not available, it must be calculated from the available geometry and material information. When a BIM model (Section 2) is used, the weights can be calculated by the BIM software or addons.

One aspect that could potentially cause discrepancies is that moisture (rain and snow) is absorbed by the concrete, making the elements heavier the longer the deconstruction takes. It can be difficult to determine in advance how much extra weight this will add, but gaining experience on deconstruction will contribute to improved estimations.

3.6. Quality management

3.6.1. Deviations and on-site reviews

As with the construction of buildings, there will always be moments in a deconstruction process that are different from what was expected. Unexpected points will have to be dealt with on the spot. A plan how to agree on dealing with deviations may be part of the

² Photo source: <https://www.hilti.nl/content/hilti/E3/NL/nl/products/bu-anchors/chemical-anchors/HVU2-foliecapsule-anker.html>

structural deconstruction plan. It should specify which experts (e.g. the structural engineer, the safety officer, a deconstruction expert) should be involved in deciding how to handle different kinds of deviations.

Equally important is that the structural engineer participates in on-site reviews during deconstruction. The purpose is to ensure that deconstruction is carried out in accordance with the structural guidelines, i.e. that it is structurally correct and safe. Incorrect deconstruction techniques can damage the precast concrete elements, resulting in additional repairs or even disqualification of the element for reuse. Quality control during the deconstruction process can mitigate or prevent this. On-site reviews can be a way to handle the deviations mentioned in the previous paragraph as well.

3.6.2. Elements' condition review during deconstruction

The physical condition of elements, i.e. whether degradation or damage is present, is one of the decisive factors for their reusability and value in reuse. The condition of the elements cannot be derived from design drawings and calculations, but must be determined through structural survey before, during and/or after the deconstruction process. Upcoming reports from a dedicated ReCreate Work Package (WP 4), such as deliverable D4.3, will instruct on the best practice process of structural survey in the context of deconstruction and reuse.

One tool for the quality management that can be a part of the structural deconstruction plan is an evaluation chart, intended for the deconstruction workers' on-site use (Figure 34). Such charts are a helpful method for checking the elements for the occurrence of damage caused by deconstruction. As a result, the elements can be classified into different quality categories, such as directly reusable, reusable after refurbishment, or non-reusable, and directed to the appropriate processes. Figure 34 showcases an evaluation chart for hollow core slabs, which distinguishes the significance of different types of cracking for reuse.

3.7. Transport and storage of elements

The correct transport and storage of elements should be described in the structural deconstruction plan or in a separate transport and storage plan. This is particularly important if the storage takes place on the deconstruction site (or another temporary storage site) and not e.g. in a precast element factory, where the workers are experienced in handling precast concrete elements. The transportation and storage methods are important because these activities should not damage the elements or pose a danger to the people handling them, let alone bystanders. Such risks can occur due to unsafe transport or storage setups, where elements can slip or break. Damage can also occur due to the weather and temperature, such as freeze-thaw damage of the elements.

Figure 34. A chart for checking and classifying hollow core slabs (source: Lagemaat).

A structural engineer’s involvement is necessary because there are structural aspects that play a role in the way elements should be transported and stored. The structural behaviour of precast concrete elements is partly determined by the orientation of the elements; the normal orientation of a wall is vertical and that of a floor slab is horizontal. The elements should as a rule be transported and stored in the same orientation. If there is a need to deviate from the ‘normal’ orientation in transport or storage, a structural engineer must provide instructions on how to lift, transport and store the element in a different orientation. Changing the orientation can result in damage or breakage of the elements.

Figure 35. Instructions for the correct storage of hollow core slabs (source: Lagemaat).

Figure 35 shows an example specifying requirements for the storage of hollow core slabs. The figure exemplifies the correct and incorrect use of wooden supports below and between slabs. Incorrect application may result in damage, as soft soil underneath the slabs can shift and change the support of the slabs so that breakage is enabled. Geometry of the elements can also be a driver as shown in Figure 36. The outer, non-load-bearing layer of the sandwich facade panels extends well below the bottom of the inner load-bearing layer. Special transport and storage arrangements are needed because the non-load-bearing layer must not be subject to loads. The use of special racks ensures that only the load-bearing layer is, in fact, loaded.

Figure 37 shows some temporary storage situations where walls are stacked at an angle. On the left of the figure, walls have been placed directly against each other. In theory, the walls may slip if there is not enough friction at the bottom of the walls. The structural engineer should provide correct and safe instructions in the deconstruction plan how to (temporary) store harvested elements. This is important not only to prevent unsafe situations as well as inadvertent damage to the elements.

Figure 36. Storage and transport of special geometry facade panels (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 37. Temporary storage of elements on site (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO [left] and Christoph Henschel, BTU [right]).

Weather protection during storage is another factor that the structural deconstruction plan should instruct about. The need for it depends on the type and properties of elements; expectations for moisture management in the given context; as well as the climatic conditions at play. In the Nordic conditions of Finland and Sweden, for example, water accumulation into the elements during storage should be prevented if elements originating from indoor conditions (made of non-frost-resistant concrete) are to be stored in outdoor conditions in the winter. Similarly, in contexts where indoor air quality is a high priority, preventing unnecessary water entry into the mineral wool insulation of sandwich panels should be considered. Alternatives to achieve weather protection are indoor storage, storage canopies, and tarps (Figure 38).

Figure 38. Weather protection of elements with tarps in outdoor storage (photo: Satu Huuhka, TAU).

3.8. Lessons learnt

Contents of a structural deconstruction plan

A structural engineer must author the structural deconstruction plan, which must cover all structural aspects related to the work safety and value preservation (damage avoidance) of the elements during deconstruction, lifting, transport and storage. However, ideally this is a discursive process with the deconstruction company because the alternatives to detach elements may depend on the skilled staff and equipment of the company. Such cross-checking and optimisation of plans will lead to a safe, efficient, and value-preserving deconstruction process.

Deconstruction of non-reusable elements

Even in a deconstruction project, not all elements can necessarily be harvested for reuse for varying reasons (e.g. because of quality or market reasons or damage incurred during deconstruction). There may be elements that will rather be recycled as materials. If some elements are identified as non-reusable from the very beginning, the labelling scheme should clearly distinguish them from elements that will be salvaged for reuse. In deconstruction, though, the non-harvested elements must in principle be treated like harvested elements, since they must be deconstructed like all other elements. It does not seem to be possible to easily combine destructive demolition with deconstruction while maintaining the donor building's stability and work safety for deconstruction workers in the building. However, the method of deconstruction, lifting, storage and transport can vary (in practice be somewhat rougher for the non-salvaged elements). The structural deconstruction plan should consider the structural aspects of such rougher methods as well. A clear distinction between the different processes for salvaged and non-salvaged elements is important to avoid inadvertent damage to the former.

Reusing a structural deconstruction plan

Some aspects of the deconstruction plan can be used in other deconstruction projects, but each project is also unique and therefore a deconstruction plan is tailor-made. Differences in deconstruction plans will depend on the type of project. Differences will be limited when

deconstructing standardised precast concrete systems and more extensive when deconstructing non-standardised systems.

Educating workers on the structural deconstruction plan

As discussed in more detail in the next chapter, the deconstruction process is usually carried out by companies that specialise in demolishing buildings and may not yet be seasoned in deconstructing each element of a building individually (Figure 39). Some of the deconstruction companies and/or workers have experience with renovating buildings, which involves similar skills and equipment as needed in the deconstruction of a building. However, in general, the companies and their workers need to configure the existing skills into a new process to deconstruct a building safely and efficiently, and without damaging the harvested elements.

The use of incorrect methods may render elements non-reusable, occur unnecessary costs (e.g. due to induced refurbishment needs that could have been avoided), or risk work safety. The workers may not be well versed to identify such issues on their own, at least not in the very beginning, when deconstruction is still novel and it has not been incorporated in their basic training. Therefore, the structural engineer authoring the structural deconstruction plan should discuss the contents with the workers prior to deconstruction. Explaining the reasons behind the instructions in the structural deconstruction plan, such as the retention of structural stability or the value of the components, will help workers to understand the consequences of deviating from the plan. Training workers can also be a part of the deconstruction process.

In principle, deconstructed precast concrete elements should be treated in the same fashion as new concrete elements, to the greatest degree possible, throughout all the processes involved in deconstruction and reuse: lifting, transport, storage, etc.

Figure 39. The essential difference between demolition (left) and deconstruction (right) (photos: TNO archives [left] and Thijs Lambrechts, TU/e [right]).

Archiving assembly plans in the future

Writing an assembly plan is standard part of a new precast concrete building project. This plan, which is authored by the precast supplier's engineer and the project contractor, describes all the aspects required to assemble the precast concrete products into a

building. It includes, for example, assembly details, a construction sequence, and clarifies specific points of interest, like cantilever structures. The plan may be available in the authors' company archives but more often is not. Should assembly plans be more widely archived in public archives, they could become valuable assets for structural deconstruction planning in the future. Archiving assembly plans should be an essential consideration in precast buildings' circularity passports.

4. Deconstruction work plan

After the structural engineer has developed the structural deconstruction plan, it needs to be translated into practical work processes for workers. The deconstruction work plan is developed by an expert in the deconstruction company, and it is a description of all aspects of the work needed to deconstruct the building safely. It can include the following topics:

- A list of the staff participating (Section 4.1) and the equipment and tools used (Section 4.2) in the deconstruction process to disconnect, cut connections between elements and to remove structural and non-structural parts from the building.
- All safety measures (Section 4.3) needed to make the deconstruction site safe for workers and outsiders alike, such as temporary fences, personal protective equipment (PPE), on-site rules for keeping the construction site clean (collecting waste, and used blades and drills etc.), and safety measures for visitors.
- A site layout (Section 4.4) with lorries' driving routes in and out, the site's internal traffic routes, positioning of the crane, a layout for harvested elements' storage and waste containers, etc.
- Schedules (Section 4.5) of all the different work phases.
- Work processes (Section 4.6) for both the harvested elements, including labelling, cleaning the elements on site, and checking their quality before transportation into (temporary) storage and for non-harvested elements and materials.

4.1. Workforce

At present, it is rare that a company would be exclusively specialised in deconstruction, with the German ReCreate industrial partner Ecosoil as an exception. Usually the companies that performed the deconstruction in ReCreate's pilots identify currently as demolition companies. However, the conventional demolition process of a whole building is entirely different from the deconstruction process. It involves consuming the building structure away by chopping it into small pieces with a long-boom excavator that stands on the ground level. The pieces are placed in a crusher, where rebar is separated and the concrete is finely ground into a secondary aggregate.

Rather than conventional demolition, the skills and equipment needed in deconstruction resemble demolition works done in the context of refurbishment and renovation of buildings. For instance, diamond sawing and drilling are used for making new apertures in concrete structures when existing buildings are renovated. Deconstruction crews should be put together from members experienced in these fields of expertise. It can also be beneficial to include workers experienced in the assembly of precast concrete buildings, who can contribute expertise on the lifting, handling, storing and transporting the elements.

4.2. Equipment and tools

During deconstruction, a variety of equipment and tools are needed to loosen and separate precast concrete elements and, in some cases, to clean them by removing excess concrete, mortar or grout. Identifying the tools needed, as well as the tools available, is an essential part of the deconstruction work planning. Knowledge about the tools is also a key consideration for the structural engineer in defining, with the help of the deconstruction company's experts, where and how (e.g. how deep) cuts can be made in the concrete structure (as discussed in section 3.4). Figure 40 to Figure 44 demonstrate the main tools used in ReCreate's deconstruction pilots. Figure 45 to Figure 48 showcase alternative tools, which may have specific purposes as a part of a deconstruction process, depending on the characteristics of the donor building as well as the deconstruction project.

Diamond drilling

Figure 40. Tools for drilling holes into the concrete. Holes are needed for post-installed fasteners or for creating space for threading chains through concrete elements (right), photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO [left] and <https://kikloopwerken.nl/gat-laten-boren-in-beton-of-steen> [right].

Hammering and chiselling

Figure 41. Pneumatic drills (hand-held and an accessory to a demolition robot) for removing concrete and screed. They are also used to loosen connections (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO [left] and Thijs Lambrechts, TU/e [right]).

Diamond sawing

Figure 42. Different types of saws are used in deconstruction. A saw for sawing vertical joints between hollow core slabs (left). A saw positioned on a rail to cut horizontal joints (right). The rail is connected to concrete walls via post installed fasteners (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Diamond saws in various models and sizes are used in the deconstruction process for cutting concrete and steel. A saw can be automated, like the one in Figure 42, or hand-held like in Figure 43. Hand-held saws are useful for cutting small pieces or in locations that other types of (larger) saws cannot easily access. Water is used to cool the blade during the sawing. The saw can be applied with a good level of accuracy.

Figure 43. Hand-held saws used for cutting joints, concrete and steel (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Milling

Screed from floor slabs can be removed with pneumatic drills or milling tools (Figure 44).

Alternative tools

Possible alternative tools which can be used in a deconstruction process include:

- A blow torch for cutting through steel, such as the steel connectors (Figure 45).
- Water jetting, if concrete needs to be removed or cut without damaging the rebar in the concrete element (Figure 46).
- A hydraulic piston for finalising the disconnection of floor slabs by jacking them up (Figure 47). The demolition robot (Figure 41, right) can be used to the same effect.
- A chain saw can be used for cutting through very large concrete elements or in locations that are physically difficult to access with other types of saws (Figure 48).

Figure 44. A milling accessory to a demolition robot (Figure 41, right) is used for milling the screed off the top of hollow core slabs (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 45. A blow torch is used to cut the connection between two walls (photo: P. Herrmann, BTU).

Figure 46. Water jetting is used to remove concrete from an element without damaging the reinforcement (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 47. A hydraulic piston to lift the cut floor slab to finalise disconnection (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Water jetting can be used to remove parts of concrete from a precast concrete element. A high-pressure water jet is used to break the concrete into small pieces. The water jet breaks the concrete but retains the rebar (Figure 46). The method is useful when the preservation of the rebar is needed, e.g. for steel grade testing purposes. It is, however, not practical on a larger scale because a lot of water is needed, and operation times are short because of work safety reasons. The method is also noisy and quite slow. The water jetting method was tested at Technical University of Eindhoven in conjunction with research into the detection of reinforcement in precast concrete elements, the results of which will be reported as a part of ReCreate's Work Package 4.

A chain saw uses a steel chain or wire covered with diamond particles. The chain is looped around a concrete element or a joint and back into the machine (Figure 48). The machine pulls the looped chain and as a result, cuts through the concrete, including the reinforcement. The method can be used in situations where the cutting location is not accessible to a regular diamond saw or when the depth of the necessary cut is particularly deep (the maximum diameter of the saw blade is 2.4 m, so the maximum cut depth is 1.2 m). It should be noted though that a chain saw's cut is not particularly accurate. The route of the chain cannot be controlled in detail, so it will move in a somewhat unpredictable manner and result in an uneven cut. The use of a chain saw was considered in ReCreate's pilots but eventually not used, as the work could also be accomplished with other tools.

Figure 48. Chain saw for cutting through big concrete elements or elements not accessible for a normal diamond saw; the chain is indicated with red arrows (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO). Note: The photos are from a deconstruction in the Netherlands, which was not a part of the ReCreate project (deconstruction of a parking garage in Dordrecht).

Crane

Depending on the deconstruction project's needs, a stationary tower crane or a mobile vehicular crane (a hydraulic loader crane) may be used (Figure 49). Some of the differences between the two types of cranes include:

- A mobile crane can be moved to another position, which makes it more flexible. This can also alter the necessary capacity of the crane due to the fact that a mobile crane can be positioned near a heavy concrete element.
- The boom of a mobile crane is always positioned at an angle, whereas the tower crane has a horizontal boom above the building. The horizontal boom touring above the building is physically incapable of hitting the building, which may add to safety. This must be taken into account when deciding which type of crane to use.
- A mobile crane can be set up very quickly, whereas the tower crane needs more time. The setup of a tower crane can take up to a week, depending on the location and the size of the crane. A mobile crane can move on its own, whereas a tower crane's relocation requires assistance from a separate vehicle and a mobile crane.
- Tower cranes can have much greater height, and this provides an advantage when deconstructing high-rise buildings.
- The tower crane is present during the complete deconstruction period, also when it is not used. A mobile crane can be commissioned to arrive on the site when needed, and the presence of the crane can be optimized.

Figure 49. Stationary tower crane (left, photo Satu Huuhka, TAU) and a mobile hydraulic lifter crane (right, photo Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Other tools

In addition to a crane, other lifting equipment for personnel and machinery may also be needed. This includes different types of person lifters and construction hoists (Figure 50).

Figure 50. Two types of person lifters (left, middle) and a construction hoist (right) (photos: Eetu Lehmusvaara, TAU).

4.3. Work safety

Work safety is a focal aspect of deconstruction work. Because of the essential differences between demolition and deconstruction, the work safety aspects of deconstruction

resemble – rather than those of demolition – those of building construction and precast element assembly. Specific work safety regulations to be followed depend on the context; the regulations in the EU level and the ReCreate pilot countries have been discussed in Halonen et al. (2023).

The foundation for (de)construction site safety is laid down in the safety education of workers, which is a part of their basic professional training. Education, training and experience ensure that people know how to do their jobs safely. There are also health and safety training courses for workers, which workers must take up regularly to stay up to date and certified to work on (de)construction sites.

Preparing a health and safety plan is an essential part of work safety planning of deconstruction sites. Since it is required to apply for a demolition permit, it is usually prepared as a separate plan, but it can be referred to in the deconstruction work plan or annexed to it. The plan identified risks involved in each type of work. For instance, chiselling with handheld power tools causes vibration, which could be a health hazard, so daily vibration exposure did not exceed the limits given in work safety regulation. Moreover, dust and noise could be a health hazard not only to the deconstruction workers but also to nearby residents. Precautionary measures were taken to prevent health problems, and companies operating in the construction and demolition industry know the appropriate measures well.

Figure 51 illustrate various safety aspects in deconstruction (instructions at the entrance of the site). Like in any construction or demolition project, the access to the site must be restricted by fencing off the area. Gated entrances should be used to manage the access. Before entering, workers must wear PPE (Figure 52) such as appropriate work clothing, hard hats, safety shoes, gloves, safety goggles, hearing protectors, and – if the work is dusty – respirators. Similar rules apply to potential visitors, who must be authorised to access the site and be accompanied by workers at all times.

Unlike demolition but similar to element assembly, falling from heights was a particular concern in the deconstruction process. There were several ways to manage the risk. In addition to providing workers with fall protection training, workers were, for instance, tethered to the building with a safety line (Figure 52). Alternatively, scaffolding and fences could be used around the donor building (Figure 53 and Figure 54) and shafts and holes must be sealed off (Figure 55). The protective fences and seals need to be moved regularly as the deconstruction proceeds.

The handling of heavy concrete elements is a work safety concern similarly as in element assembly. It must be ensured that the elements do not fall, and people or body parts do not become crushed under their weight. One should never walk underneath a concrete element while it's being lifted. Since many deconstruction workers have a background in the demolition industry, they are normally not readily used to handling concrete elements. Therefore, it is appropriate to provide rigging training at the start of deconstruction. Such training involved theory about lifting and attaching of loads to the crane, as well as practical hands-on exercises. The use of radiotelephones is also a key measure to keep

workers informed about where and when lifting takes place, so that they know to avoid accessing the part of the site where elements are being lifted.

As a rule, lifting safety requires that elements must be fully loose before lifting, because pulling the elements with the crane could subject both the building and the crane to unpredictable dynamic stresses, which they have not been designed for. During deconstruction, all the connections of an element are cut, but there is always a possibility that the element is not entirely free for a controlled lift, which is a risk factor. The aspect needs to be considered; the crane driver and workers need to be aware of the risk and react accordingly to avoid unsafe situations.

Figure 51. Overview of a deconstruction site (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 52. PPE, including harnesses and safety lines to limit the impact of falling (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 53. Scaffolding can add extra safety to the working environment on the deconstruction site (photos: Christoph Henschel, BTU).

Figure 54. The use of fences can be used as an alternative to using a safety line (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 55. In all potentially dangerous situations, measures should be taken to protect the workers. In this case, this means closing a hole in the floor and fencing off the lift shaft (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

4.4. Site planning

Transport routes

Whether the elements, once harvested, can be transported out of the deconstruction site is a key factor for whether they are available for reuse. Traffic arrangements around the donor building may have changed since its initial construction, so planning the transport routes, taking into consideration turning radii and heights of lorries, is one of the first considerations to make. Transportation companies can advise on the dimensions of alternative vehicles and trailers for the job.

Crane placement

The site plan features information about the location(s) of the crane, whether a stationary tower crane or a mobile crane. The BIM model of the donor building can be used for analysing the best location(s) for the crane on site. These spots can be determined by comparing the distance-dependent lifting capacity of the crane, the weight of the elements (e.g. from the inventory BIM model), and the distance between the crane and each element (Figure 56).

Figure 56. Using a BIM model to determine the placement of the crane, in this case a mobile crane (source: Lagemaat).

Element storage

The space for storing harvested elements on site depends on the location and size of the donor building’s plot, as well as the surroundings (e.g. whether land can be rented temporarily from adjacent plots). The site plan should determine the arrangements of the on-site storage. The availability (or the lack thereof) of immediate storage space is directly connected to the scheduling of logistics (Section 4.5), too, as less space to store calls for more frequent transportations to separate storage locations.

Waste handling

During the deconstruction process, also waste is created. The handling and material separation of the waste needs to be determined as a part of the work plan – i.e. whether the recycling of non-reusable elements and materials takes place on-site or at a separate

location. The placement of waste containers (Figure 57), whether on ground or on the floors of the donor building, should be defined in the site plan, and the emptying frequency in scheduling of logistics (Section 4.5). If there is a need to place containers in the building, a structural engineer must always be consulted first to ensure the capacity of the floor structure is not exceeded (see Section 3.3). Alternatively, a waste chute can be used, the location of which should be determined in the site plan. The best location will depend on the situation, but it is advisable to optimise it to reduce walking distances.

Figure 57. A steel container is placed on the building during deconstruction. All the waste created during deconstruction is collected in this container and sorted later on (photo: M. Vullings, TNO).

4.5. Scheduling

Scheduling is an important tool for monitoring the progress of a process and is therefore an integral part of deconstruction. When a deconstruction work plan is prepared, the necessary tasks are mapped out and this information can be used to prepare a detailed implementation timetable.

Scheduling and timetabling are the basis for the deployment of personnel, equipment and special measures, such as temporary road closures and transport arrangements. It makes clear which elements will be released and when they need to be lifted or transported. This process is made more flexible if elements can be temporarily stored on site.

Conventional scheduling tools

Gantt charts (Figure 58) are normally used for scheduling projects. On the left side of the chart, all the tasks are presented in specific order. The order represents the sequence of the actual activities done. The horizontal axis on top of the chart represents specific time periods, like weeks, months or years, depending on the length of the project. The projected duration of each task is presented by a bar in the chart. By positioning this bar in a certain week or month, a timetable is made.

At each point in time, the status of a project can be determined by marking the progress of each task, see the red dotted line in the Gantt chart (Figure 58). Figure 59 and Figure 60 show different methods to plan, monitor and visualise the progress project. In addition to charts, floor plans can be used to plan or document the actualised progress of the deconstruction by time stamping the date of deconstruction for each element (Figure 60).

The timetables should be constantly monitored as the deconstruction proceeds and updated as necessary to facilitate the completion of the deconstruction despite potential delays due to deviations and/or unforeseen events (e.g. weather restrictions or change of plans due to matters encountered on site, such as ways of connecting elements that differ from the original drawings).

The examples presented are more conventional method for scheduling and timetabling of a deconstruction project. The next section shows an example of a new method were 3D BIM model of a project is used.

Figure 58. Example of a Gantt chart, a typical chart for making timetables. The project progress is marked by the red dotted line.

Figure 59. Overall planning chart of the deconstruction process (source: Skanska).

Figure 60. Documentation of actualised timing of deconstruction. The different colours represent different dates of deconstruction. (source: Skanska).

BIM-aided scheduling

Another effective method of visualising the schedule is to link it to the BIM model of the donor building, so-called 4D BIM (Figure 61), where time is the fourth dimension. 4D BIM is normally used in simulating the construction process of a new building but it can also be applied to a deconstruction process. Tasks in the schedule are linked to individual elements, and by selecting a given date, the BIM model shows the expected status of deconstruction by that date. A 4D BIM animations can be used to clearly visualise the deconstruction tasks and sequence and can assist with identifying conflicting activities, incorrect sequences of tasks and, if needed, adjustments can be made to optimise the deconstruction schedule. 4D BIM can be seen as a digital deconstruction of the building. The evaluation and optimization process can also be done with other types of scheduling, like the Gantt charts and Excel sheets, but in recent years 4D BIM has proven to be more effective and efficient. The evaluation and optimisation of the schedule should involve the project members, as they can provide specific feedback. For example, a structural engineer can detect possible errors in the sequence of removing elements from the structure and prevent (partial) loss of structural stability of the building during deconstruction.

Figure 61. 4D BIM scheduling. The deconstruction of the complete building (left). Several stages of the deconstruction process of the lower wing (right) (source: Lagemaat).

Figure 61 (left) showcases the use of 4D BIM for analysing the deconstruction sequence. Reviewing the first version helped to identify necessary changes to the plan, such as doing the deconstruction in stages, rather than at one go. The 4D BIM analysis revealed that phasing the deconstruction was a much better strategy. The deconstruction as performed in two different stages, the first one as the deconstruction of one wing of the building and the second stage is to deconstruct the other wing and core together. This ensures the stability of the building during deconstruction and is speeds up the process because it limits the need to move the crane. This method also provided the opportunity to test the

deconstruction process on a small part of the building first. Consequently, the final deconstruction sequence was as follows: first the lower wing of the building (Figure 61, right), then the high wing (nine storeys), and the central core of the building was deconstructed together with the high wing, but at a slower rate.

4.6. Work processes

Work processes planning determines how workforce (Section 4.1), tools (Section 4.2) and safety measures (Section 4.3) are combined into processes that implement the structural deconstruction plan (Chapter 3) in space (Section 4.4) and time (Section 4.5). It needs to consider the deconstructed building overall (Section 4.6.1), each type of element (Section 4.6.2), and any supportive processes that are necessary (Section 4.6.3). Distinct workflows are needed for elements that are salvaged and for structures and materials that are only recycled. The latter processes are business-as-usual, so unlike the former ones, they will not be elaborated on the current report.

4.6.1. Overall workflow

Table 1 lists a general set of tasks in a deconstruction workflow for demonstration purposes. However, the actual deconstruction sequence is always given in the structural deconstruction plan. In some projects, the order may differ, an extra step is needed, or a specific task may not be a part of the process. The list in Table 1 is not exhaustive, and the structural deconstruction plan always takes precedence.

Table 1. Overall deconstruction workflow.

#	Task
1	Setting up the building site (including utilities, fencing, portable toilet, construction lift etc.)
2	Hazardous substance removal and stripping.
3	Labelling all the elements in the building. Alternatively, the labelling can be done storey-to-storey.
4	Assembling a tower crane or positioning of a mobile crane and all the other equipment and materials.
5	Adding the safety measures at the working level and other unsafe locations.
6	Positioning temporary bracing supports.
7	Making preparatory works, if allowed by the structural deconstruction plan. These may include screed removal on top of slabs, grout removal in connections to reveal steel connectors, and making preliminary ('halfway') cuts. Such works may also proceed in parallel with the deconstruction.
8	Hooking the first elements to a crane and cutting the connections and joints as defined in the structural deconstruction plan. The first elements could be roof

	panels (top floor slabs) or balustrades and/or parapets, if present. The correct sequence is described in the deconstruction plan.
9	Lifting the deconstructed elements one-by-one out of the building to a storage on site.
10	Cleaning the elements in the on-site storage area (if needed) and transporting the elements to a storage facility.
11	Deconstructing the next elements (such as beams, columns, walls, etc.) as per the sequence given in the structural deconstruction plan. The last elements to be removed from each floor are stability elements, typically walls and sometimes facade elements. Repeating #9 and #10 for each element type.
13	Unless already done in step #3, labelling all the elements of the next storey.
14	Moving the safety measures and bracing elements one storey down.
15	Repeating the steps #8 to #14 until all storeys have been deconstructed.
16	Dismantling the site (removing the fences, the scaffolding and (if present) the tower crane, etc.)

Besides the tasks in this list, some tasks are ongoing throughout the deconstruction process, such as the assessments of the elements, quality control of the process, transporting elements to a storage facility, adding and (re)moving fences (at the edge of the building and shafts) and other safety measures, collection and removal of waste, etc.

4.6.2. Workflows of main precast element types

This section illustrates deconstruction workflows for different types of elements. The examples are by no means exhaustive, and their details may slightly differ from the ones implemented in ReCreate’s pilots (cf. Vullings et al. 2024), but the purpose is to demonstrate key principles. Deconstruction of precast concrete elements share common steps, which are applicable to all types of elements. An important consideration when harvesting precast concrete elements for reuse is not to damage them (cf. Section 5.1). To prevent damage, elements are harvested by cutting only the connections between elements at the joints. Damage and/or changes to the original shape and/or reinforcement of an element may limit the reuse, as it usually means a reduction of the structural capacity, and it can even lead to the need to disqualify elements from reuse. In addition to the shared principles, there are also specific steps that are unique to a particular element type.

Floor slab elements

The deconstruction process of floor slabs is as follows (the shared steps included):

1. Placing temporary supports underneath the floor slabs to secure the slabs that will remain in the structure after one slab has been removed. Removing one slab could cause unforeseen movement of other slabs and possible unsafe situations.

2. Cut all joints surrounding the floor slab(s). The order of sawing and disconnecting all connections must have been determined by the structural engineer in the structural deconstruction plan, with the focus being on disconnecting one floor slab without the occurrence of any unforeseen loosening of the other slabs.
3. The subsequent application of the lifting tools and hoisting the floor slab is then carried out, with the crane operator monitoring the lifting force to establish that the slab is fully detached from the structure. Should the lifting force be greater than the weight of the element, this indicates that the element is not fully detached and that all the connections must be re-checked.

A diamond saw is typically used to cut the joint between two hollow core slabs (Figure 62) or between a hollow core slab and a wall, including the connections (steel ties, rebar or anchors). An automated saw was used in several of the deconstruction pilots. The cutting depth of the saw can be set by the operator of the saw. The correct depth when cutting floor slabs depends on the situation, this aspect proved to be crucial in the pilot projects, as shown in Section 5.1.

Figure 62. Cutting of the longitudinal joint between floor slabs with an automated floor saw (left). (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Both the longitudinal joints and transfer joints between hollow core slabs (Figure 63) are disconnected with the saw. In the longitudinal joints between two slabs, there are typically no connections, like ties, rebar or steel connectors. In the transfer joints, steel connectors are present, connecting the hollow core slab to another element, either another hollow core slab or a supporting beam (2 in Figure 63), a wall or a facade (3 in Figure 63). In some situations, the longitudinal sides of hollow core slabs are connected to walls or facades, presented in the original details (Figure 64 and Figure 65). While such elements are possible to harvest, one way to deal with their more laborious deconstruction is to sacrifice them to harvest the other slabs more quickly. This was done in the Finnish pilot, where the connection was eventually not sawn but chiselled. These slabs were rejected from reuse.

It is possible to push up the floor slab to loosen the floor slab completely before lifting it away. This action can be used to determine whether the element is completely loose and

to avoid possible overloading the crane, or to break the last remnants of a possible connection, as in the Dutch pilot project. In it, the cutting depth was intentionally set at 20 millimeters less than the thickness of the floor to reduce the wear and tear of the saw blade. The last 20 millimeters of concrete were disconnected by lifting the floor slab with a hydraulic piston (Figure 47) underneath the slab. In the Finnish pilot, the same effect was achieved by jacking the slab up with a demolition robot.

Figure 63. The vertical joints between hollow core slabs. The longitudinal joints are marked with a red arrow (1) and the transfer joints are marked with yellow arrows (2 & 3) (photo: Thijs Lambrechts, TU/e, amended).

Figure 64. Three vertical cross sections of the connection between a hollow core slab and a wall parallel to the span of the hollow core slab. The red lines marks the location of the cut to undo the connection between the precast elements (source: [A&B] Ramboll, [C] Province of Gelderland, all amended).

Figure 65. Two vertical cross sections of the connection between a hollow core slab and a load bearing wall perpendicular to the span of the hollow core slab. The red lines marks the location of the cut to undo the connection between the precast elements (source: [A] Ramboll, [B] Province of Gelderland, all amended).

Hollow core slabs are not the only type of precast concrete floor slabs, but they provide a good illustration of the type of connections, the joints and the methods used to harvest floor slabs. These types of joints and connections can also be applied to other floor systems.

Walls

The deconstruction process of wall elements is as follows (the shared steps included):

1. The walls are secured, including the wall which will be harvested, to prevent any potential collapse or damage during the deconstruction process. Securing is achieved by using temporary braces, which are employed to prevent the wall in question from falling over during the removal process.
2. Lifting devices are installed and the wall in question is connected to the crane in order to facilitate the removal. Existing lifting anchors in the element may in some cases be used (as in the Dutch pilot), or alternatively, lifting holes have been drilled through which lifting chains or pins are threaded (as in the German and Finnish pilots). The appropriate methodology is determined by the structural engineer.
3. All joints around the wall are cut with a diamond saw. Once the element has been cut loose, it is lifted by the crane and the crane operator monitors the lifting force. Any discrepancies in the lifting force indicate the presence of uncut joints and needs to be dealt with. Once the wall has been lifted, it is ready for transportation to storage.

Walls have two horizontal joints, one at the bottom of the wall and one at the top. In the previous section, the joints and connections between walls and floor slabs are presented. To present the relationship between the horizontal joint between two walls and the joint between a wall and floor, both cuts are marked in the next details. Red lines indicate the joints between two walls and a blue line indicate the joints between wall and floor slabs (Figure 66 and Figure 67).

The vertical joints at the left and right side of the wall are typically joints between two walls. Steel connectors or rebar are usually used to connect the elements, but they are not always present in vertical joints between walls (like in the Dutch pilot project). Sawing of the vertical joints between walls may not be even necessary, because they may only be filled with a low-quality mortar or flexible sealant. In this situation, no special disconnection process may be needed, because the sealant or mortar is broken simply by lifting the element.

Columns

Columns are load bearing elements which typically support a column, a beam, or both. Different types of connections are used for connecting columns to columns and beams, but the ways of disconnecting can be quite similar. In the example from the Finnish pilot, the top column must be removed by cutting the steel ties between the beam and the top column (Figure 69, right). The bottom column's connection to the beam becomes disconnected as the beam is disconnected (see next section).

Figure 69. To disconnect the top column, the steel ties need to be cut (marked by red lines in the detail on the left). A hand-held saw was used to cut these steel ties (right). Sources: Ramboll [left], amended, and Emmi Salmio, TAU [right].

A very different type of connection is found in an additional Dutch deconstruction project 'Ter Haak' in Amsterdam (Vullings et al., 2024), as shown in Figure 70 (A), but the deconstruction technique is similar. Starter bars have been cast into the top of the column, and beams with grout tubes are positioned over the projecting bars. A next column, also fitted with grout tubes is placed on top of the beams. Figure 70 (B) shows the same type of connections when connecting two columns directly. The columns can be harvested by making a horizontal cut in the joint between the column and the beams with a diamond saw.

Figure 70. The connection between two columns can via one or two beams (A) or direct (B). Starter bars are cast in the top of the column and are positioned in grout tubes at the bottom of the next column and/or beams (source: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Beams

The deconstruction of beams follows a very similar process to that of walls:

1. If necessary, the elements are temporarily supported in accordance with the structural engineer's specifications.
2. The beam in question is coupled to the crane. This involves utilising existing lifting anchors or holes drilled in the beam ahead of time.
3. All couplings are then disconnected, and the beam is lifted. The crane operator monitors the lifting load and, should it deviate, all connections are re-checked and cut. The beam is then lifted and transported to storage.

Beams need to be supported by other structural elements, like a columns or walls. In the previous section's examples, the beams are supported by columns. In order to disconnect the connection between the beams and columns, the grout tube in the beam is drilled out with a hollow cylinder drill from the top of the beam (Figure 71). After drilling, the connection is disconnected, and the beam can be lifted. The same type of connection is used when a beam is supported by a wall and therefore the same deconstruction method can be used.

In some cases, connections similar to the ones in Figure 69 (left) may not be filled with grout. In that case, the connection may be disconnected by simply removing a nut from a threaded steel rod connecting the column below to the beam above. Such a connection can even be reused in the next new structure.

Figure 71. A detail of a connection between a column and two beams (left). After drilling out the grout tubes in the beam the beam can be lifted (right) (source: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 72. The right beam is lifted from the top of the column after disconnecting the connection (source: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

4.6.3. Supportive processes

Hazardous substance removal

As outlined in Table 1, specialised hazardous substance removal needs to take place before stripping to guarantee the safety of deconstruction workers and users of the surrounding area as well as the non-contamination of the elements to be harvested for reuse. As per best practice, it is recommended to have a dedicated demolition plan for hazardous substances. The plan should be based on a comprehensive hazardous substance survey,

performed by a qualified professional (cf. Section 3.1). The demolition itself should also be performed by qualified professionals, equipped with appropriate PPE to protect their health, taking necessary precautions to prevent the dissemination of the substances to the surroundings, and delivering the demolished material to appropriate treatment facilities.

Stripping

Before starting the deconstruction, all non-structural elements, installations and superfluous architectural finishes (e.g. windows and doors, suspended ceilings, internal dividing walls, fixed furniture, floor coverings, wall finishes, pipes, etc.) must be removed, leaving only the structure of the building visible (Figure 73 to Figure 75). Together with hazardous substance removal, stripping can take a lot of time, depending on the size of the building, the presence of hazardous materials and the overall complexity of this phase. All dismantled parts are collected for reuse, such as doors, plumbing, etc., and all other materials are separated and recycled. These preparatory activities ultimately enable the actual deconstruction of the building structure, i.e. harvesting the precast concrete elements. Exposing the structure also enables taking measurements of the concrete structure and material samples, where necessary (cf. Chapter 2).

Figure 73. Every part of the building is being stripped and either reused or recycled. Metal-framed internal walls and supported ceiling is stripped (left). Installations are removed (right) (photos: Thijs Lambrechts, TU/e).

Figure 74. The same area (lift doors) during stripping (left) and after, during the deconstruction (right). All the internal walls, doors, lifts and installations have been removed ahead of deconstruction (photos: Thijs Lambrechts, TU/e [left] and Marcel Vullings, TNO [right]).

Figure 75. Donor buildings during stripping, internal dividing walls already removed (photos: Thijs Lambrechts, TU/e [left] and Inari Weijo, Ramboll [right]).

Screed on top of floor slabs is a special item in stripping, as it is firmly connected to the slab below. It is not a structural part of the floor slabs, though, and brings no benefit in a new structure. It also breaks easily and can be a hazard when transporting the floor slabs. Pneumatic drills and milling tools can be used to remove a screed with a thickness up to 80 mm (Figure 76). Without the screed, the (hollow core) floor slabs also resemble conventional new products more so than with the screed attached, potentially making them easier for practitioners to accept in reuse. Instead of screed, floor slabs may also have reinforced structural topping. The removal of structural topping can be difficult, and it may need to be left in place (see Section 5.1.1).

Figure 76. Removal of the screed (photos: Emmi Salmio, TAU [left], Jacob Fischer, BTU [right]).

Moreover, some of the finishes on the elements themselves, such as thin screeds on vertical surfaces or paint, may be intentionally left in place. They can be removed as a part of the refurbishment process if the new use requires the removal e.g. for aesthetic reasons. However, if the surfaces do not remain visible, there may be no need to remove them at all.

Physical tagging of elements with labels

The labelling scheme for tracing, developed by a structural engineer (Section 3.2) needs to be implemented physically on site, before the elements are lifted down from the donor building. The ReCreate paper Dervishaj et al. (2023b) describes several alternative methods for applying a label to an element, such as QR or bar codes, RFID tags etc. In the ReCreate deconstruction pilots, the codes were applied by painting or tagging a label with a QR code to the element (Figure 77). Both ways could also be used together for surety: the codes were painted on the elements before deconstruction, and corresponding labels with QR codes were attached on the ground for transport and storage purposes. When using labels, the long-term durability of both the material and the ink against weather, such as sun and rain, must be ensured, not to lose the code at any point in time. The benefit of digital tags, such as RFID chips, embedded in concrete is that they are better protected from falling off during deconstruction, transport and storage. ReCreate's Work Package 3 gives further account of some methods for tagging elements and the possibilities of using the tags for tracking the elements and for the pairing of the physical elements with its digital counterpart (and the information carried by that or linked to that). Companies of the value chain, such as element manufacturers, may have ready in-house tracking systems that can be harnessed for this purpose.

Figure 77. Labelling of individual precast concrete elements in the donor building (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Preparing elements for transport

In many cases, the joints between precast concrete elements are filled with grouting concrete, which sticks to the sides of elements even after deconstruction. To ensure a safe transport with no concrete chunks falling off from the elements during transportation, the elements must be sufficiently cleaned on site (Figure 78). This type of work can also be done in-between tasks when the workers would otherwise be waiting. The degree of cleaning on the deconstruction site may vary. As long as the elements are clean enough to be transported, additional cleaning can be carried out later in storage or in refurbishment.

Figure 78. Cleaning hollow core slabs for transportation with a pneumatic drill (photo Eetu Lehmusvaara, TAU).

Additionally, if the local environmental authority classifies the elements as waste, the site personnel shipping the elements away needs to be aware and take care of completing the required paperwork.

Keeping the worksite clean

A work process that should not be underestimated is cleaning. Deconstruction also produces waste material, such as waste grout. Keeping the worksite clean helps to reduce risks, such as tripping. Employees who have no immediate tasks at hand should clean the site and remove waste materials at all times. Cleaning and recycling waste must be part of the work plan and work ethics at a deconstruction site.

4.7. Lessons learnt

Contents of a deconstruction work plan

The deconstruction company authors the deconstruction work plan. It should cover all work and site-related matters necessary to safely implement the structural deconstruction plan (Chapter 3) in practice. Quite often, not all parts of the plan are put down explicitly in writing, as work planning is tacit knowledge of the deconstruction companies. A comprehensive written plan is nevertheless advisable for learning and replication purposes. At the very minimum, key parts, such as a health and safety plan, a site plan, and timetables and schedules, must be available in the written form.

The structural engineer should be kept in the loop during work planning for contingency planning reasons. For instance, if workers with certain kind of expertise or equipment cannot

be engaged in a timely manner, alternatives can be devised in discourse between the deconstruction company and the engineer. This helps to ensure safe and efficient deconstruction work and the preservation of value of the salvaged elements.

Necessary skills and knowledge

All the essentials of deconstruction work already exist outside of the context of deconstruction. Suitably skilled personnel equipped with appropriate tools (most importantly for diamond sawing and drilling) are conventionally employed in demolitions works for renovation projects. Concrete elements are lifted and handled when precast buildings are assembled. Site planning and scheduling is done in the context of normal construction and demolition works. Work safety considerations are an everyday aspect in these trades.

In deconstruction work planning, the existing knowledge and skills are simply reconfigured into new processes, which enable salvaging the elements safely and effectively. The structural deconstruction plan (Chapter 3) largely defines the directions for the work plan. The know-how of a deconstruction company's experts determines how well they are able to understand the findings of the pre-deconstruction audit and the content of the structural deconstruction plan, and how effectively they can translate them into a feasible work plan. The more experience of different kinds of deconstruction projects is accumulated, the more predictable these projects will also become in terms of techniques, timelines and costs.

Work safety planning

Ensuring the health and safety of deconstruction workers and outsiders is crucial. Workers in the demolition industry are used to dealing with work safety issues and the existing knowledge can be drawn from. However, hazards in deconstruction also differ from those normally encountered in demolition, due to the essentially different nature of the activities, and some of them may be novel to the workers. The importance of safety planning cannot be emphasised enough, and every precaution must be taken to avoid accidents, particularly related to falling from heights and getting crushed under heavy elements.

5. Deconstruction

This chapter reports on:

- Learnings acquired by implementing the structural deconstruction plans and deconstruction work plans in real life (Section 5.1), often from mistakes, and
- Insights on equipment, including those developed in ReCreate as well as further development needs (Section 5.2).

5.1. Findings on specific element types and deconstruction processes

5.1.1. Hollow core slabs with or without structural topping

Hollow core slab floors may come either with a thin screed for levelling or a thick concrete topping with structural purposes. If only screed has been applied, then typically a low-strength concrete class (C20/25) has been used to grout the joints between hollow core slabs in accordance with manufacturers' guidelines. In such cases, the joint grout can be removed easily and the distinctive edge profile of a hollow core slab can be restored. The result is a harvested hollow core slab which does not significantly differ from a new slab (Figure 64).

Figure 79. Harvested hollow core slab without a structural topping and with the typical edge profile on the longitudinal edge of the slab (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Alternatively, a structural topping may have been added in situ on top of the hollow core slabs to give the slabs extra structural capacity and/or to increase diaphragm action. This practice where is quite common e.g. in the Netherlands. The concrete class of the structural topping is typically C35/45 or C45/55. When the structural topping is being cast, the longitudinal joints between the hollow core slabs are also filled with the same concrete. This also increases the structural capacity of the joints. However, the practice makes deconstruction more difficult. It is not possible to restore the original edge profile and top of the hollow core slabs (Figure 80) without a great effort and a high risk of damage to the elements. Thus, the structural topping and the new straight vertical edge become a part of the harvested slabs. The topping and edge grout have no structural function in the harvested slabs, they only add weight and thickness to the slab.

Figure 80. Harvested hollow core slabs with a structural topping and a characteristic vertical edge (left) vs. new slabs with a typical edge profile (right). (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

5.1.2. Cutting inadvertently into adjoining walls

Figure 81 shows a schematic vertical cross section of a floor and load-bearing wall where the longitudinal joint between hollow core slabs was cut with a saw. Due to the circular shape of the saw blade, not the entire joint was cut but a triangle was supposed to be left at the end and beginning of the floor slab, which was to be broken off with another tool (a hydraulic lift underneath one floor slab). Moreover, the depth of the cut was designed not to go through the floor but to leave about 20 mm as also uncut. This was to reduce wear and tear of saw blades. The last 20 mm was broken by jacking the slab up from below with a hydraulic lift. This left a straight line at the bottom of the slabs and a straight edge profile.

In practice though, the saw was pushed beyond the end of the slab and cut into the next element, in this case the wall (Figure 81 and Figure 82). There is a risk of cutting not only the wall but also the reinforcement in it. This can have negative consequences for the structural integrity of the wall elements. They, including necessary further investigation and possibility

to implement repair measures, will be addressed as a part of ReCreate’s Work Packages 4 (quality management) and 5 (design of new buildings with reused elements).

Figure 81. The saw is inadvertently pushed into the wall, cutting into the rebar (source: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 82. Cuts into the facade wall (red arrows). It is unknown at the time of writing if the reinforcement in the wall is also cut or damaged (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO, amended).

5.1.3. Cutting inadvertently into beams below

Another risk to adjoining elements concerns beams when joints between hollow core slabs are sawn (Figure 83). Unlike in the previous example (Figure 81), the sawing depth had not been determined in the structural deconstruction plan. This resulted in inadvertently cutting into the supporting beam in two different directions (Figure 84), i.e. damage and refurbishment needs to the beam and its reinforcement. Since the saw depth was set manually each time without paying attention into this, the depth of the cuts vary.

Figure 83. Cut AB is made along the length of the beam supporting the hollow core slabs (Fig. 69 A and B). Cut CD is made in the longitudinal joint between two hollow core slabs (Fig. 69 C and D), photo Marcel Vullings, TNO, amended.

Figure 84. Penetration of the saw blade to the beam if set too low, whether cut along the length of the beam (A and B) or perpendicular to the beam (C and D), source: Marcel Vullings, TNO.

The significance of the cuts still needs to be addressed as a part of ReCreate's Work Packages 4 (quality management) and 5 (design of new buildings with reused elements). However, should the saw have been set correctly, i.e. to correspond to the thickness of the floor, the cuts and respective inspection and refurbishment needs and costs could have been avoided.

5.1.4. Cutting inadvertently into columns

In Section 5.1.2 and 5.1.3 precast concrete were damaged by sawing into one element and damaging inadvertently another element. In these situations the saw was pushed beyond an edge limit or the cutting depth of the saw was incorrect. The use of a diamond saw in one of the other deconstruction projects resulting in damaging columns in a other fashion, the columns were not cut at the joint at the base of the columns but a few centimeters above the joint (Figure 85). This resulted in cutting the rebar in the columns and making the precast concrete column shorter.

Figure 85. Harvested precast concrete columns, which were damaged due to the incorrect positioning of the saw. The yellow arrows mark the connections (starter bar in grout tube) between two columns which need to be cut. The red arrows mark cut rebar and the white arrows point to a fracture of the column (photo's: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 86. (A) is vertical cross section of the base of a column and the red dotted line marks the used position for the saw to cut and undo the connection and (B) shows the end result with the end not cut but fractured (source: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 86 (A) shows the position of the joint at the base of the column versus the location of performed saw cut, centimeters above the joint. During the cutting of the column in some cases the last bit of the concrete fractures (B, white arrow). This inaccurate cut resulted in damaging the reinforcement of the column (red arrows), made the column centimeters shorter and the bottom of the column was uneven. Before reusing these columns they will need some extra attention from the structural engineer in order to determine their structural fitness for reuse.

5.1.5. Non-preventable damage to adjoining elements

The fourth example deals with a situation where additional drilling was carried out to disconnect the connection between a wall and a beam (Figure 87). Figure 88 shows a section of this type of beam to wall connection. There was a recess in the wall and the beam was positioned into this recess; the wall supported the beam. To make a structural connection, starter bars and grout tubes were used (Figure 88, left). To disconnect the beam from the wall, a cylinder was drilled from the top of the beam (Figure 88, middle). After this the beam should have been free and simply lifted off the wall (Figure 88, right). This was the case for most beams, however for this particular beam, disconnecting the starter bars from the top of the beam was not enough to get the beam disconnected. Two additional horizontal cylinders were drilled just below the beam to make another cut into the structural connection, the starter bar cast in the wall (Figure 89). After some effort to pry the beam loose, the two connections were finally disconnected, and the beam was lifted

out of the building. Drilling the extra cylinders under the beam however also damaged the reinforcement in the wall.

Unlike the previous examples, this damage was not preventable since the beam refused to detach without the measures taken. However, similar to the previous cases, the incurred damage needs to be addressed as a part of ReCreate’s Work Packages 4 (quality management) and 5 (design of new buildings with reused elements).

Figure 87. A beam in a building is supported by a wall. The beam is structurally connected to the wall via starter bars in grout tubes (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 88. Vertical cross section of a beam to wall connection (source: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 89. The wall with the recess for the beam and the two cylinders drilled just below the beam to cut the connection between wall and beam (source: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

5.1.6. Weather conditions

Temperature

In regions with subzero temperatures, such as Finland and Sweden, deconstruction should be scheduled so that the stripping can take place in the winter, enabling as much as possible of the structural deconstruction to be timed between spring and autumn. The lack of daylight is a nuisance in winter deconstruction that can be addressed with artificial lighting (though with monetary and environmental costs).

Even more importantly though, freezing makes deconstruction more difficult in many respects. Unlike in demolition, in deconstruction salt cannot be used to prevent water used by the deconstruction equipment from freezing. This is because the salt would be absorbed into the elements, where it might contribute to the corrosion of reinforcements. To keep the equipment operational, the water supply may need to be kept constantly open (also during breaks), which increases water usage. The water then freezes overnight, and slipping becomes an additional safety concern. Heater mats can be used to turn the ice back into water, but their usage consumes energy. Moreover, the water can accumulate inside the hollow cores of slabs without a way to escape when it freezes and expands, leading to extensively damaged, non-reusable slab elements. This risk mainly exists when the elements are still attached to the building structure. After the slabs have been deconstructed and the hollow cores cleaned, the excess water has an escape route, so the risk is no longer relevant.

Wind

Extreme winds can also affect deconstruction by limiting the ability to lift elements. It is not possible to solve this problem by scheduling a deconstruction project only in the summer. To ensure safety, it may be necessary to stop the lifting of elements in extreme wind conditions. The maximum wind speed can be determined in the deconstruction work plan. Extra time should be allowed in the project timetable for delays due to extreme weather conditions, as is done in regular construction projects, too.

5.1.7. Partial deconstruction

Partial deconstruction is a special type of deconstruction, where the remaining structure is preserved. Some special considerations result from this, which can have an effect on the planning and implementation of deconstruction. The remaining structure must be taken into consideration. The considerations may include:

- Is the remaining structure vacated or occupied? Deconstruction can take place in occupied conditions, but users need to leave the building during deconstruction works. The building can remain in use outside of working hours.
- The remaining structure must be protected the weather during the process. A temporary shelter can be used to protect it from rain outside of working hours. A lightweight space frame with a membrane, which is lifted on and off, can be used for this purpose (Figure 90). A similar solution could be useful for controlling water and ice accumulation during deconstruction in winter conditions (cf. Section 5.1.5).
- The exposed structure needs to be finished after the deconstructions is complete. For instance, if a building is lowered, an intermediate floor may became the new roof and needs to be fitted with a roofing material.
- New elements may be needed for the remaining building, such as balusters at the edges of the building or open shafts.

Figure 90. At the end of a working day a temporary shelter can be erected on top of the remaining building. The shelter protected the remaining building from rain and other weather conditions until a new roof has been built (photo: Christoph Henschel, BTU).

Deconstruction can also be partial if it is combined with demolition, rather than refurbishment, of the remaining structure (Figure 91). Depending on how activities can be sequenced (and which activity is more dominant), deconstruction and demolition can be a challenging combination for workers mindset-wise, as their aims are contradictory: preserving elements vs. destroying a building. The order of operations must be carefully devised so that the precast elements to be harvested are not damaged. This could be achieved by doing deconstruction first and demolition afterwards, but this depends *inter alia* on the location of the elements to be harvested. Other sequences may also be feasible.

Figure 91. Partial deconstruction where one part of the building precast concrete elements were harvested and the other part of the building was demolished and materials were recycled (photo: Jonas Linné).

5.2. Development of deconstruction equipment

Several types of equipment used in deconstruction, such as pneumatic drills, diamond saws and drilling equipment, have been discussed in section 4.2. The current section 5.2 focusses on the further development of tools for deconstruction purposes.

5.2.1. Cranes

Depending on the type of the crane, it may be more or less apt for deconstruction. Deconstruction is not a use case that would necessarily have been considered when developing a crane.

For instance, tower cranes may require the driver to set the approximate weight of load before lifting, which is why the weights of the elements should be available to the driver. The correct setting of lifting power is important for work safety. Too little lifting power, and once an element is loose, it may drop and crush people or body parts (unless shores are in place). Too much lifting power, then again, may theoretically send the element jumping up and down uncontrollably like a jo-jo. For this reason, cranes should not be used for pulling elements, either.

Even though the weight of the load is pre-set, at least some tower crane models may still require the driver to physically hold the controls to maintain the exact correct lifting power while workers in the building are making the final cuts to fully detach an element. This calls for the driver to remain attentive over extensive time periods, making the crane work in deconstruction more intensive and strenuous for the operator than in building construction. Tower cranes could be accommodated for deconstruction purposes by including a taring switch (a 'trim') that would enable the machine to hold the weight while letting the operator to free their hands in the meanwhile. However, as already discussed, the accumulation of water or ice in the elements, either from rain or from the deconstruction itself, may change the weights during deconstruction. This fact requires adaptation and note taking from the tower crane operator.

Mobile hydraulic loader cranes, which are intended for lifting varying loads, may already come with taring automation built in, which substantially eases the operator's work. Such cranes can also be considered more stable when the exact weight of the load is not known (e.g. as a result of water and ice accumulation). Their downside is the more limited reach of the boom, as discussed in section 4.4.

5.2.2. Lifting accessories

As discussed in section 3.5, lifting tools for hollow core slabs had to be specially developed in the Finnish and Dutch deconstruction pilots (Figure 30). They were separately developed but share similar principles. While some commercial alternatives exist, such lifting accessories as the ones developed in the pilots are not yet available for purchase on the market but should be provided by lifting accessory manufacturers to make the mainstreaming of deconstruction easier. However, neither of the developed accessories can be considered as 'final', as room for improvement was also observed while using them.

Both developed tools require four holes to be drilled in each hollow core slab. During deconstruction, the use of the Dutch accessory was eventually omitted to reduce the number of holes required. The steel part in the slab holes was omitted, leaving only the steel chains, which run through one hole and is looped around the edge of the slab (Figure 92). Instead of four holes, the new lifting arrangement halved the number of required holes to two. There were initially concerns whether the chain would damage the edge of the slab. However, in practice, no damage occurred. The ReCreate partner Lagemaat continues using the chain method (Figure 92) in other deconstruction projects.

In the Finnish pilot, different lifting accessory alternatives were also designed but only one was selected for implementation. The manufacture of other alternatives would have required investment, but it may have paid off during the deconstruction as reduced personnel costs. One of them would have omitted the need to drill holes in the slabs altogether. Furthermore, the alternative method could have sped up releasing the slab from the lifting accessory once on ground, potentially reducing the need for personnel there. In choosing the lifting accessory to be manufactured, ReCreate industrial partners involved in the deconstruction gave precedence to established, safe processes. It should also be noted that the potential efficiency gains from the alternative lifting accessory remain theoretical, as the accessory was not yet tested in practice.

Figure 92. The new Dutch lifting arrangement for hollow core slabs omitted the newly design lifting tool (Figure 30 [left]) and used this chain variant (sources: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

5.2.3. Precision cutting

The equipment presented in section 4.2 for cutting and drilling into concrete is not sufficiently accurate in every situation. In general this has not proved to be a problem, but in some cases, such as when cutting through bottom joints of columns (Section 5.1.4), it could be helpful to make very precise cuts and drills.

A semi-automated sawing system was tested in cutting horizontal joints between two walls (Figure 93) and between walls and floors. In this setup, a rail is attached to the concrete wall and an automatic saw is attached to the rail. The saw automatically moves along the rail from one side to the other. The rail can be positioned with a degree of precision to make more accurate cuts. The saw can be positioned on either side of the rail and the rail itself can be positioned in any direction on the wall. The system proved to be very effective.

Figure 93. A semi-automatic saw was use for cutting walls. The rail is connected to the concrete via post-installed fasteners and can be positioned in any direction (photos: Thijs Lambrechts, TU/e).

If more flexibility is needed, other solutions are available to achieve greater accuracy and efficiency in future projects. Remote-controlled demolition robots can be very effective and decrease physical strain from the deconstruction work for the workers. They were in fact used in the pilots (cf. Figure 41, right), but only with rough hammering and milling accessories. However, accessories for precision sawing and drilling are also available to them (Figure 94).

Figure 94. Demolition robots with precision drilling and sawing accessories (photos ³).

5.3. Lessons learnt

Deconstruction plans, techniques, and equipment

The experience from ReCreate’s deconstruction pilots shows that the devised structural deconstruction plans and deconstruction work plans were feasible and resulted in salvaging a substantial number of precast concrete elements for reuse (see also Vullings et al. 2024). While a few pieces of novel equipment had to be developed for lifting, deconstruction could be performed effectively using mostly existing skills and tools. Nonetheless, some mistakes were also made, and the success of the deconstructions can only be fully evaluated once the reuse processes also proceed further. Adjustments to existing equipment could improve the efficiency of deconstruction even further, as discussed in Section 5.2.

Crew size

The ideal crew size for the deconstruction of a precast concrete building was determined to be around 8-10 people. This matches the size of a precast concrete building’s assembly

³ Left: <https://www.hilti.com/content/hilti/W1/US/en/business/business/trends/jaibot.html>
 Right: <https://echidna-usa.com/demolition>

crew. The number of workers was not directly related to the size of the donor building. A greater group of workers would appear to be impractical because:

- It can be difficult or even impossible to start the deconstruction process in two or more locations in the building, for reasons pertaining to the structural integrity and stability of the building (this is defined in the structural deconstruction plan though).
- Working in multiple locations makes it difficult to keep track of the work being done in each location. This means that workers at location A may not be aware at all time what workers at location B are doing. Additional measures, such as the use of radiotelephones, may be required to ensure the safety of all employees.
- More work in the same amount of time increases the number of elements that need to be lifted. The availability of the crane is critical, and an extra crane adds extra costs.
- Working in multiple locations means needing double the amount of equipment. In some cases it also means doubling the number of workers on the project. This will also add to the cost of the project.

Dealing with deviations

Structural deconstruction planning, and consequently, deconstruction work planning of a building is largely based on the original design drawings of the building. During deconstruction, it may turn out that some aspects of the building (e.g. connection details) were implemented in way that deviates from the drawings. Such deviations can result in lost time. It is therefore important to allow some flexibility in the schedule to deal with deviations. The less information is available about the building structure, the more surprises can be expected. Having a structural engineer pre-plan alternative disconnection spots and methods (Section 3.4) in collaboration with the deconstruction company is a way to avoid delays on the site. Deconstruction workers may also propose alternatives, but it is essential to have the structural engineer review such proposals before implementation, as there may be structural considerations (stability or other) influencing work safety that the workers, based on their education, do not know to take into account.

Avoiding preventable damage

As discussed in sections 5.1.1 – 5.1.2, even small deviations from the structural deconstruction plan can have adverse consequences for the value of elements. Cutting into elements' reinforcement incurs further investigation, required to determine the presence and extent of actual damage and whether it is a structural issue that may lead to repair needs or even disqualification of the elements for reuse.

As demonstrated in section 5.1.3, damage may not always be preventable. However, when it is (as in Sections 5.1.1 and 5.1.2), action should be taken to prevent it, because the additional inspection and refurbishment measures bear unnecessary costs. For instance:

- The involved workers should be educated in advance about these types of situations by a structural engineer. This can be done during the presentation of the structural deconstruction plan to the involved parties.

- The workers can present a problem encountered at the site to the structural engineer, so that the engineer can provide a solution that does not result in structural problems.
- A structural engineer can do routine quality control visits to the deconstruction site to observe potential problems in the work process. The regular presence of the engineer on site also allows the workers to approach the engineer more easily.

Influence of weather

In Fennoscandia and other similar climatic regions, snow and extreme cold can have negative effects on deconstruction work, affecting all kinds of aspects. Energy and water usage increases. Water freezes, making sawing difficult and surfaces slippery. The ability to perform tasks efficiently and safely is reduced in extreme cold and this can lead to unsafe situations. Planning a deconstruction to take place in the spring-summer can help to avoid extreme weather and associated problems.

In coastal regions, problems caused by high winds cannot be managed through timing deconstruction for a given season. However, additional days should be built in the schedule for changing weather conditions.

Post-deconstruction evaluation

Part of the learning curve is the evaluation of the deconstruction process, as done in this chapter. The evaluation should be done with all parties involved, including the deconstruction workers. Mutual learning, of individuals and organisations alike, is valuable for the next project. All lessons learnt should be used in future projects, not only in the deconstruction process, but also in the preparation and formulation of future deconstruction plans.

6. Recommendations

This final chapter recaps and summarises the main recommendations given in the previous chapters. Please consult the whole report, though, for sub-process specific, smaller insights.

6.1. General recommendations

#	Recommendation
1	Successful deconstruction calls for several plans to be made by different experts (such as the structural deconstruction plan and the deconstruction work plan, with sub-plans like health safety plan, lifting plan, site plan, schedules, etc.). To ensure that all plans are well aligned, all experts should be aware of the content of all plans and cross-check. If necessary, they can point out inconsistencies, inaccuracies and improvements and together optimise the plans. The aim is a safe and efficient deconstruction, where all elements are harvested without any damage.
2	Deconstruction of precast concrete elements for reuse is novel, so there will be a learning curve. Include mutual teaching and learning moments in the process, such as regular quality checks, evaluations and instructions for all involved. Create a list of improvements and a 'lessons learnt' section for each project to facilitate personal and organisational learning.
3	New precast buildings' assembly plans should be more widely archived for the long term, as they are useful for structural deconstruction planning.
4	Learnings acquired from ReCreate and future deconstruction projects should also be incorporated in developing future precast concrete structures with 'Design for Disassembly' (DfD) principles.

6.2. Pre-planning with BIM model

#	Recommendation
5	The creation of an inventory BIM model should be a normal step in a deconstruction project. The model is a good way to store, combine, access, analyse and visualise data about the donor building.
6	Use the BIM model to check the gathered data for accuracy, completeness and conflicting information. It helps to identify gaps and clashes in the geometry.
7	A model based on drawings should be verified by comparing it to the physical structures. Check the information, such as geometry, on site, during

deconstruction, and/or when the harvested elements are in storage. Changes due to deconstruction can be observed and incorporated into the model so that subsequent steps can be performed with the correct and up-to-date information.

6.3. Structural deconstruction plan

#	Recommendation
8	The structural deconstruction plan must be authored by a qualified structural engineer, preferably in dialogue with the deconstruction operator.
9	The plan must cover all structural aspects related to work safety and elements' value preservation in the deconstruction of the donor building as well as subsequent steps, namely lifting, transport, and storage.
10	If some elements of the donor building are scheduled for reuse but others are destined for recycling, clear labelling schemes and deconstruction processes must be developed for each to avoid inadvertent damage to elements to be salvaged.
11	A deconstruction plan can be reused, but only as a template for a new project. Each building's structural features must be considered individually. When dealing with highly standardised precast concrete systems, more aspects of a plan can likely be reused.
12	Educate deconstruction workers about key structural considerations, such as the donor building's structural stability during deconstruction and how elements should be handled to avoid breakage. This is essential to ensure work safety and good quality of the salvaged elements.

6.4. Deconstruction work plan

#	Recommendation
13	A deconstruction company's expert(s) should author a deconstruction work plan to translate the structural deconstruction plan into work processes. A comprehensive plan in writing is recommended, as this enables organisational learning and replication. Key parts, such as a health and safety plan, should always be in writing.
14	Skilled personnel and tools to perform deconstruction work exist, so the main task of deconstruction work planning is to configure those skills and tools to feasible processes. In addition to available workforce and equipment, the work plan should cover work safety, site location and layout, the overall process and schedules, and element type specific deconstruction processes.
15	Work safety planning is of utmost importance because health and safety risks of deconstruction differ essentially from those of demolition. Serious

precautions must be taken to avoid falling from heights, being crushed under elements, etc., in addition to more conventional safety concerns.

6.5. Deconstruction

#	Recommendation
16	Existing equipment, such as lifting accessories for precast elements, could be made more fit for deconstruction purposes with small adjustments. Manufacturers should provide deconstruction-optimised equipment more widely on the market.
17	Deconstruction crew size should ideally be 8-10 people, similar to the assembly of a precast building.
18	Leave a margin in the timetable for unforeseen situations because some deviations will likely occur during the deconstruction of a building. Have a structural engineer pre-plan alternative deconstruction methods, or agree on a low-threshold discursive process with the structural engineer to quickly deal with deviations on-site to ensure the safety of the workers, the stability of the building and the quality of harvested elements.
19	Make use of a quality control system to prevent preventable damage from being incurred on salvaged elements. The structural engineer should be involved in quality control procedures and perform regular on-site quality checks.
20	Prepare for the occurrence of extreme weather conditions in timetabling and otherwise. Take precautions to ensure the safety of workers, the building and harvested elements.
21	Invite all involved parties to take part in post-deconstruction evaluation. Deconstruction is novel, so individuals and organisations alike can gain and contribute valuable learnings that can be put to use in future deconstruction projects.

7. Conclusion

When it comes to the overall experience of the ReCreate deconstruction pilots, a picture emerges that deconstruction is not to be mistaken for a different form of demolition. Even though the efficiency of the deconstruction process has been and can be further improved, the total process time of a deconstruction, including the pre-deconstruction audit, information gathering, and BIM modelling, etc., will likely never compare to the time of conventional destructive demolition. When considering the significance of this, it is important to remember that unlike in demolition, the aim of deconstruction is not simply to remove a structure. Harvesting elements for reuse is essentially a form of production, which substitutes for virgin production.

While virgin elements are precast in a factory, harvested elements are deconstructed from a donor building, tested, cleaned, and (if necessary) refurbished. In both forms of production, there is a preparation phase, which includes information gathering, 3D BIM modelling, making plans, and so forth. They also share a storage stage: harvested elements are stored in a temporary facility, while the new elements are stored on the production site. In both cases, the elements are transported to a new site and mounted into a new building structure; this is the ultimate objective of both processes. A comparison between deconstruction and conventional demolition of buildings should be made on an equal footing, including (in the case of demolition) the transformation of waste concrete into new precast elements, with all that follows (an engineering process with 3D BIM modelling and detailing, production with quality controls, transport, and construction of a new building). These aspects will be elaborated on in future ReCreate deliverables from Work Package 6, which deals with Life Cycle Assessment and Costing (LCA and LCC).

The deconstruction pilots of the ReCreate project reinforced the notion from the experience preceeding ReCreate: deconstruction and reuse of precast concrete elements are feasible within current construction practices. Improvements and optimisations are possible and with more experience, the number of projects will also increase. Some observations that support this entail:

1. Business models are currently being developed in different countries by the industrial partners of the ReCreate project as well as their competitors.
2. In new building projects, more thought is given to reusing building elements, e.g. by designing for disassembly (DfD). There are already several commercial products on the market for implementing DfD connections.
3. Entire building systems have been and are being developed that focus entirely on circular construction, such as reusing materials and DfD.
4. All kinds of guidelines, regulations, tools, and processes are being developed that support and promote reuse of elements in construction.
5. ReCreate offers a wealth of practical experience and new knowledge. This is already being utilised by ReCreate partners (including the universities) in the development

of improvements and tools, as well as for the creation of new solutions in the field of connections.

The reuse of precast concrete elements will not be the sole solution in the fight against climate change, but it is undoubtedly one of the solutions that is deserving of a place in the construction practice of the near future.

References

Dervishaj, A., Fonsati, A., Hernández Vargas, J., & Gudmundsson, K. (2023a). Modelling Precast Concrete for a Circular Economy in the Built Environment. In W. Dokonal, Hirschberg Urs, & G. Wurzer (Eds.), *Digital Design Reconsidered - Proceedings of the 41st Conference on Education and Research in Computer Aided Architectural Design in Europe (eCAADe 2023)* (pp. 177–186). eCAADe, TU Graz. <https://doi.org/10.52842/conf.ecaade.2023.2.177>

Dervishaj, A., Hernández Vargas, J., & Gudmundsson, K. (2023b). Enabling reuse of prefabricated concrete components through multiple tracking technologies and digital twins. *European Conference on Computing in Construction and the 40th International CIB W78 Conference*, 4, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.35490/EC3.2023.220>

EN 1992-4. *Design of concrete structures – Part 4: Design of fastenings for use in concrete*.

Halonen, T., Räsänen, A., Jonker-Hoffrén, P., Huuhka, S., Malmqvist, T., Al-Najjar, A., Vullings, M.W.F., Wijte, S.N.M., Fischer, J. & Henschel, C. (2023). *Legal and technical requirements in reusing precast concrete*. The ReCreate project.

Räsänen, A., Lahdensivu, J., Gudmundsson, K., Dervishaj, A., Westerling, H., Lambrechts, T., Vullings, M., Arnold, V. & Huuhka, S. (2024). *Properties and quality of precast concrete elements deconstructed in ReCreate's pilots*. The ReCreate project.

Vullings, M.W.F., Wijte, S.N.M., & Huuhka, S. (2022). *Guidelines for a BIM-aided pre-deconstruction audit*.

<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5f54ee881&appId=PPGMS>

Vullings M.W.F., Wijte S.N.M., Henschel C., Fischer, J., Huuhka, S., Salmio, E., Räsänen, A., Lahdensivu, J., Gudmundsson, K., Stenberg, E., Westerling, H. & Dervishaj, A. (2024). *Real-life deconstruction pilots of the ReCreate project*. The ReCreate project.

Annexes

Annex 1. Deconstruction documents

The following deconstruction documents were used in the preparation of this report.

#	Author	Document title	Country
1	Ramboll	Deconstruction plan, guideline	FI
2	Ramboll	Deconstruction plan, floor plans	FI
3	Ramboll	Deconstruction plan, lifting instructions	FI
4	Skanska	General deconstruction timetable	FI
5	Skanska	Timing documentation of implemented deconstruction	FI
6	Anders Amilon	Floor plans of the warehouse	SW
7	Lagemaat	Analyses, reuse Prinsenhof A	NL
8	Lagemaat	Deconstruction lifting plan	NL
9	Lagemaat	Deconstruction flow chart	NL
10	Lagemaat	Product info, braces	NL
11	Lagemaat	Product info, fasteners	NL
12	Lagemaat & IMd	Deconstruction plan	NL
13	Lagemaat & IMd	Deconstruction structural analyses IMD	NL
14	Ecosoil	Deconstruction technology	DE
15	Ecosoil	Deconstruction plan	DE
16	Architect Günter Wenzel	Drawings, deconstruction and retrofitting of roof	DE